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SONNETS

***Societal Needs aNalysis and Emerging Technologies
in the public Sector***

Deliverable D3.1

**SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for
the Public Sector**

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Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	10
1.1	PURPOSE AND SCOPE	10
1.2	APPROACH FOR THE WORK PACKAGE AND RELATION TO OTHER WORK PACKAGES ..	11
1.3	STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT.....	12
2	SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK FOR THE PUBLIC SECTOR.....	14
2.1	THE VISION OF TRANSFORMING THE PUBLIC SECTOR INTO AN INNOVATION BREEDING CARRIER	14
2.2	DEMAND-DRIVEN INNOVATION FOR ADDRESSING PRESSING AND EMERGING SOCIETAL NEEDS	15
2.3	THE ROLE OF ICT IN PUBLIC SECTOR INNOVATION	16
2.4	THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK METHODOLOGY.....	18
2.4.1	Background	18
2.4.2	Overview	19
2.5	STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED	22
2.6	INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION WORK METHODS	25
2.6.1	Desk-based research	25
2.6.2	Interviews	26
2.6.3	Focus groups / Workshops.....	27
2.6.4	Brainstorming and Discussion	29
2.6.5	Online Consultation	30
3	STEP BY STEP METHODOLOGY	31
3.1	OVERVIEW OF THE FRAMEWORK	31
3.2	NEEDS IDENTIFICATION	34
3.3	TECHNOLOGY IDENTIFICATION.....	35
3.4	TECHNOLOGY SELECTION AND ANALYSIS	37
3.5	TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT	38
3.6	INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION.....	40
3.7	SCENARIO BUILDING.....	52
3.8	VALIDATION	58
4	ONLINE CONSULTATION OUTCOMES.....	60
5	NEXT STEPS.....	65
6	CONCLUSIONS	67
7	REFERENCES.....	70
I.	APPENDIX A: GUIDELINES FOR INTERVIEWS WITH PRIVILEGED INFORMANTS (NEEDS-FOCUSED INTERVIEWS).....	72
II.	APPENDIX B: GUIDELINES FOR INTERVIEWS WITH IT EXPERTS (TECHNOLOGY-FOCUSED INTERVIEWS).....	78
III.	APPENDIX C: TECHNOLOGY / TREND ANALYSIS TEMPLATE.....	80
IV.	APPENDIX D: TECHNOLOGY / TREND ASSESSMENT TEMPLATE	81

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: WP3 STRUCTURE AND DEPENDENCIES WITH OTHER WPS/TASKS	12
FIGURE 2: THE GOALS OF THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK	19
FIGURE 3: THE ROLE OF THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK.....	21
FIGURE 4: METHODOLOGY FLOW DIAGRAM	22
FIGURE 5: NEEDS IDENTIFICATION PHASE	34
FIGURE 6: TECHNOLOGY IDENTIFICATION PHASE.....	36
FIGURE 7: TECHNOLOGY SELECTION AND ANALYSIS PHASE.....	37
FIGURE 8: TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT	39
FIGURE 9: INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION PHASE	41
FIGURE 10: "PUBLIC SECTOR MODERNIZATION" IMPACT ASSESSMENT AREAS	42
FIGURE 11: "PUBLIC SECTOR AS AN INNOVATION DRIVER" IMPACT ASSESSMENT AREAS	45
FIGURE 12: OVERVIEW OF IMPACT AND FEASIBILITY ASSESSMENT DIMENSIONS.....	50
FIGURE 13: SCENARIO BUILDING PHASE.....	52
FIGURE 14: FORESIGHT METHODS CLASSIFIED BY THEIR ESSENCE (SOURCE: POPPER, 2008)	53
FIGURE 15: EXTREME POINTS IN A 3D SCENARIO SPACE.....	54
FIGURE 16: PROBABLE FUTURES AND THE DESIRABLE ONE	56
FIGURE 17: VALIDATION PHASE	58
FIGURE 18: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES WITH REGARD TO THE USE OF A FRAMEWORK FOR INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION (Q1).....	60
FIGURE 19: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES WITH REGARD TO THE STARTING POINT OF THE INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION PROCESS (Q2)	61
FIGURE 20: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES ON POTENTIAL FRAMEWORK OMISSIONS (Q3)	61
FIGURE 21: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES WITH REGARD TO THE MOST IMPORTANT STEP OF THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK (Q4).....	62
FIGURE 22: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES WITH REGARD TO THE MOST DIFFICULT TO IMPLEMENT STEP OF THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK (Q5)	63
FIGURE 23: DISTRIBUTION OF PARTICIPANTS' RESPONSES WITH REGARD TO THEIR WILLINGNESS TO USE THE SONNETS INNOVATION IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK (Q7).....	64

List of Tables

TABLE 1: DEFINITIONS, ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	7
TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT	25
TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE SONNETS FRAMEWORK METHODOLOGY.....	33
TABLE 4: SONNETS SCENARIOS KEY UNCERTAINTIES AND POSSIBLE VALUES	56

Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym	Title
EC	European Commission
EGDI	UN E-Government Development Index
EU	European Union
HCI	Human Capital Index
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OSI	Online Service Index
PS	Public Sector
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threads
TII	Telecommunications Infrastructure Index
WP	Work Package

Table 1: Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

Executive Summary

The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework is an innovative methodological framework that will accelerate the transformation of the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The goal of the SONNETS Framework is twofold and lies in supporting innovation both **in the public sector** and **through the public sector**.

Innovation in the public sector may have an internal or external focus, pertaining to the improvement of the public sector internal processes and the former's efficiency, and the development of improved services for citizens and businesses respectively, and targets the public sector's modernization. On the other side, ***innovation through the public sector*** focuses on promoting the generation and implementation of innovative ideas and the corresponding creation of value in other sectors and pursues accordingly the transformation of the public sector into an innovation driver.

The Framework emphasizes the necessity to have an informed view of the current societal trends and challenges as a prerequisite for better accommodating the respective needs, as well as the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a key enabler for innovation, and pursues its goal by means of coupling findings on emerging ICTs and trends with insights on current societal challenges and needs. Such coupling is carried out on the basis of specifying and bringing into the foreground specific innovative solutions for the adoption of the identified technologies and the confrontation of the identified needs respectively. In this respect, the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, and more specifically the innovation solutions specified are considered as the means to bridge the identified needs with technologies.

The Framework does not limit though its scope in the specification of relevant innovation solutions. It further addresses the assessment and evaluation of their actual innovation potential. The latter is considered under the prism of both the impact and feasibility of the identified solutions. To this end, the Framework defines a set of impact assessment criteria and feasibility assessment criteria, in order to evaluate the innovation potential of the solutions under consideration for the public sector. The former are used to evaluate the magnitude of the potential effects of the identified solutions, whereas the latter are employed to assess the research needs, which the technological, socio-economic and ethical implications

of these solutions translate into. The rating of the specified solutions against both the dimensions of impact and feasibility allows distinguishing and, possibly prioritizing, those solutions that hold greater value for the public sector, and lays the foundations for designing a concrete time plan of actions and a set of recommendations for their implementation in practice.

From a methodological point of view, the SONNETS Framework relies basically on the methods of desk-based research, interviews, focus groups and workshops, and open consultations, and encompasses six logical steps or phases as follows:

- i) the identification of societal needs, societal and public sector trends/challenges ([Needs Identification](#))
- ii) the identification of emerging technologies and trends that make a difference today in other sectors ([Technology Identification](#))
- iii) the selection of a subset of these technologies and trends, and the analysis of the latter in terms of their key characteristics and specificities ([Technology Selection and Analysis](#))
- iv) the assessment of these technologies in the domains originally met and their correlation to the public sector needs and societal challenges on the basis of existing services and applications, as well as new innovation solutions that may benefit from these technologies ([Technology Assessment](#))
- v) the evaluation of these services’ and solutions’ innovation potential in terms of both their impact and feasibility ([Innovation Identification](#))
- vi) the selection among the former, of those that make more sense to be ported to the public sector through the development of adequate scenarios ([Scenario Building](#))
- vii) the evaluation and ratification of the overall findings ([Results Validation](#)).

The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework has guided the innovation identification activities within the SONNETS work-plan, but can also be used as a self-standing innovation framework for the public sector.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

SONNETS is guided by the vision to provide the guidelines and a methodological process that will help to reshape and reform the public sector into a technology leader and innovation breeding carrier, playing a key role in technology development and showcasing. In this respect, the project targets the development of an ever-evolving methodological framework, backed up by an active community, driven forward by renowned experts and interested public sector officials and practitioners, for the rapid porting of emerging technologies into public sector services and into policy domains where innovation co-exists with increased effectiveness and efficiency. Thereby, a key component in the SONNETS work plan is the identification and analysis of emerging technologies and trends and the assessment of their innovation potential for the public sector. At this point, attention is drawn to the fact that in the context of the SONNETS project and the present deliverable, the terms “technologies” and trends refer exclusively to emerging ICTs and ICT trends respectively.

The present deliverable is released within the context of Work Package 3 “Identification of Emerging Technologies and Innovation Identification Framework” and is in particular associated with Task 3.1 “SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Definition”. The latter has strong links with Work Package 2 and the needs’ identification procedure and targets to lay the foundations for all the work to be conducted in this WP, and in particular to provide, in the context of a high level methodological framework, the description of activities, alongside with the guidelines and criteria, required for:

- The identification of societal trends and needs.
- The identification of current and emerging societal needs and the innovation requirements of the PS that could be translated into concrete innovation actions by the PS.
- The identification of emerging technologies and trends related to public sector.
- The interlinking of novel technologies and technological breakthroughs with the different societal and public sector needs identified in the previous WP (WP2).
- The assessment of those trends’ impact in the domains observed.
- The drawing of the relations of those trends to the public sector and to the different policy domains.
- The projecting impacts of the adoption of those technologies to the public sector.

Along the above lines, the objective of this deliverable is to provide the aforementioned framework, entitled “SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for the Public Sector”, and thereby the methodology for collecting, analysing and cross-checking the viability and applicability of emerging ICTs in the public sector.

The framework, which has been validated both by means of relevant offline and online activities (encompassing the SONNETS Experts Focus Group in Torino in September 2016, Athens Validation Workshop in February 2017 and an online consultation, running from 01/06/2017 to 31/07/2017) is primarily intended to guide activities within the project and in particular within the rest of WP3 tasks, but may also be considered as a self-standing methodological aid for supporting the public sector's ICT transformation.

The deliverable at hand presents the revised and validated version of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework along with the outcomes of the recently held online consultation.

1.2 Approach for the Work Package and Relation to Other Work Packages

Work package 3 concerns, as already explained in Section 1.1, the development of the Innovation Identification Framework, and the identification of emerging technologies. It is a component of the project, active from the start of SONNETS until M12 that enumerates four interdependent tasks and is intended to produce three deliverables, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Task 3.1 is the introductory task to WP3, specifying through deliverable D3.1 the activities to take place in the following. Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 are concerned with the actual identification of emerging technologies and their analysis and impact assessment respectively, with their outcomes being compiled in deliverable D3.2, which stands as an initial list of emerging technologies and applications that could prove useful for the public sector. Finally, Task 3.4 pursues the validation and updating of these outcomes with the engagement of the targeted stakeholders, the results of this process being reported in deliverable D3.3.

Figure 1 below further illustrates Work Package 3 dependencies to the rest of SONNETS WPs. These include the use of deliverable D3.1, namely the Innovation Identification Framework as the means to couple WP2 and WP3 results both in the context of Task 3.3 on the identification of potential applications and services for the public sector and of their innovation potential for the latter, as well as within the frame of the gap analysis to be conducted in Task 4.2. They further include feeding Task 3.4 outputs, and thereby deliverable D3.3, to WP4 and its first task (Task 4.1) on the analysis of the most promising technologies.

Figure 1: WP3 structure and dependencies with other WPs/tasks

1.3 Structure of the Document

The document at hand is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the rationale behind the development of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for the Public Sector, and thereby exposes the vision of bringing the public sector at the forefront of innovation promoting activities. In respect to that vision, it further discusses on the necessity to possess knowledge on the challenges and problems currently encountered by the public sector, the current societal trends, challenges and emerging needs, the innovation requirements of the PS, innovation actions the PS can undertake to address societal challenges and needs as well as on the key role of technological developments in fostering public sector innovation. Section 2 additionally provides an overview of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, whereas it also outlines the stakeholder groups to be involved and details the innovation identification methods to be employed.
- Section 3 exposes the revised and updated SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology on a step by step basis. Each step of the methodology is in particular presented in terms of its goal, work methods, inputs and outputs, while the plan of its implementation within the project context is also provided.
- Section 4 exposes the findings of latest of the validation activities that have taken place in the context of the SONNETS project and the application of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework in particular, i.e. the outcomes of an online consultation that has been active from June 2017 to end of July 2017.

- Finally, Section 5 outlines the next steps and opens up further directions for the potential extension and enrichment of the framework beyond the end of the project, while
- Section 6 summarises the contents of the deliverable and reports relevant conclusions.
- A number of Appendices incorporate a set of guidelines for conducting interviews and guiding discussions in focus groups, as well as a set of templates for carrying out the related analysis and impact assessment tasks.

2 SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for the Public Sector

2.1 The vision of transforming the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier

The public sector plays a key role in the society and the economy as regulator, service provider and employer. In addition to that, it is also responsible for fostering innovation in the private sector by providing funding to private companies, and contributing to the development of key technologies by investing on these in the early stages of development, when uncertainties for private companies are too high. Due to its role as a service provider in particular, the public sector is also - and has always been - the receiver of intense pressures for increasing its productivity, providing more efficient and citizen-centric services and enhancing democratic participation.

Nowadays, however, technological breakthrough and innovations, emerging trends, such as those of increased globalisation and mobility of people, goods and services, demographic change and ageing societies, chronic diseases, climate change, degradation of the natural environment and gradual depletion of its resources, and changing lifestyles create a complex and turbulent environment that is challenging the role of the public sector as perceived so far. On top of that, in the wake of the economic crisis, stressed public finances bring public sector organisations up against long-term challenges and problems, such as high unemployment rates, rising social security and health care costs, an outdated in several cases public service infrastructure that lags behind the current needs of citizens and businesses [1], and generally even greater pressures for producing “more with less” [2]. In this environment, public sector organisations, agencies and departments are cast into roles, where they must not only react to the crisis, but be pro-active problem solvers and seek new opportunities for value creation.

Along the above lines, the role of the public sector is changing from one that is expected to ensure stability, resilience and continuity to one that must also embrace a strategic and systematic effort to manage emergence of and create positive change [3], or, simply put, to innovate. In fact, in addition to the public sector's role in *catalysing innovation in the wider economy*, there is an urgent need to power innovation *within the public sector itself* in order to unlock radical productivity improvements and efficiency gains, to foster the creation of more public value and a better response to societal challenges [1].

Innovation in the public sector can be defined as the process of generating new ideas, and implementing them to create value for society [4], and may have an internal or external focus, pertaining to the development of improved processes or services respectively [5]. In particular, the European Commission identifies policies and initiatives for public sector innovation along three axes: (a) policies and initiatives with an internal focus on enhancing public sector efficiency, (b) policies and initiatives with an external focus on improving services and outcomes for citizens and businesses and (c) policies and initiatives with a focus on

promoting innovation in other sectors [6]. Overall, the goal is both *innovation in* the public sector (with internal or external focus), and *innovation through* the public sector (fostering innovation elsewhere).

These axes pertain to the vision of *transforming the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier* and are further in line with the goal of public sector innovation as defined by the OECD Observatory of Public Sector Innovation: “*to use new approaches, from policy design to service delivery, for a high performing, more responsive public sector*” [7].

2.2 Demand-driven innovation for addressing pressing and emerging societal needs

Since the end of the nineties, a significant amount of attention has been devoted to what was initially named eGovernment and subsequently also referred to as public sector innovation. As a consequence, a considerable amount of public resources were devoted to promote the digitalization and the improvement of government agencies’ processes. Twenty years down the road, the results achieved are still considerably below expectations. The EU eGovernment Report 2016 recently published highlights how “online public services are becoming increasingly accessible across Europe, 81% being now available online. However, deeper analysis of user-centricity, transparency, cross-border mobility and in general quality of use shows that growth is uneven and a substantial number of EU countries are still lagging behind. This sends a clear signal for acceleration, in order to keep up with private sector pressing needs, and citizens’ expectations” [8].

The reasons for such results are manifold, nevertheless it may be said that part of the problem lies in the technological determinism and lack of citizen/customer orientation that characterized the management of the innovation process. As a matter of fact, any given innovation in the public sector may be considered valuable only to the extent to which it allows to attain a set of objectives that are perceived as being of intrinsic value either for society or for a specific target group of stakeholders. In other words, ICT is a means to an end [9].

The perception of value is strictly correlated with the needs of a society. In this respect, it is useful to mention that individual as well as collective needs may be hierarchically organized in order to provide a priority ranking. The work conducted at the beginning of the last century by the American psychology Abraham Maslow represents a cornerstone in this field [10]. His hierarchy of needs identifies five categories of needs having to do with physiology, security, belonging, esteem and self-actualization. In a resource constrained situation, such classification could represent a useful tool in identifying and prioritizing the long term strategic priorities that should be targeted in order to create value for the society. A value that - as Savitz [11] reminds us - unfolds along a number of dimensions touching upon financial, social, environmental aspects. We refer the reader to D2.1 for a more in depth discussion of the role of needs in innovation.

The notion of a demand-, or value-, driven innovation is emerging across academia and the world of practice. The business model ontologies tools

developed by Alex Osterwalder [12], [13] as well as the lean start-up methodology developed by Eric Ries [14] implicitly rely on the identification of the needs a given innovation intends to address as well as an early and intense involvement of the final users in the testing phases. It is also well recognized that involving and engaging with citizens and relevant stakeholders in the innovation phases and processes is crucial to implement local needs-oriented innovation [15]. To institutionalize this practice, the starting point is to ensure a thorough analysis of the emerging and societal needs of various stakeholder groups in the public sector.

The innovation framework proposed by the SONNETS project incorporates a demand driven component that increases the chances of orienting the innovation activities towards a better alignment with pressing and emerging societal needs. This is done by including in the methodology a number of data collection and co-creation activities that are detailed in D2.1.

2.3 The role of ICT in Public Sector Innovation

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is widely accepted as a key enabler for innovation, particularly when referring to related disruptive technologies or technological breakthroughs that change the nature of products and services; not to mention, that it is usually the main factor to which the conversation narrows down when the question of how to achieve innovation is addressed.

One of the main reasons that ICT is considered capable to drive innovation is the fact that it is characterized by high flexibility and adaptability, so it can be used in many different ways and for many different purposes in various sectors of the economy, and enable important innovations in the business processes, products, services and business models of organisations [16].

Further, ICT has dramatically reduced various groups of costs, with particular impact on costs related to information processing and transfer. ICT has also removed many of the factors that imposed limitations in the production process, heavily affecting parameters such as time and place [17]. Moving closer to the public sector and the public service conceptualization, design and delivery domain in particular, ICT can lead in big productivity increases, costs' reduction and increased output quality [18]. The design of new products/services and improvements of important intangible aspects of existing products/services, such as convenience, timeliness, quality and personalization, also constitute factors that can be heavily ameliorated through the use of information and communication technologies [17].

Overall, technology may incarnate or simply underpin several forms of innovation in the public sector including, according to the typology by Windrum (2008) [19]:

- Service innovation, i.e. introduction of a new service product or an improvement in the quality of an existing one.
- Service delivery innovation, namely new or altered ways of delivering to clients, or otherwise interacting with them, for the purpose of supplying specific public services.

- Administrative and organizational innovation which stands for changes in the organizational structures and routines by which front office staff produces services in a particular way and/or back office staff support front office services.
- Conceptual innovation, mapping to the development of new world views that challenge assumptions that underpin existing service products, processes and organizational forms.
- Policy innovation, i.e. changes to the thought or behavioural intentions associated with a policy belief system.
- Systemic innovation and, thereby, new or improved ways of interacting with other organizations or knowledge bases.

Yet, in spite of its vast potential, technology has no value on its own. To make a difference, it has to be appropriately applied to solve specific problems, address specific challenges or meet certain goals, as defined by an organisation itself and its customers. In fact, it is only when technology is combined with insights on what customers want, that real innovation can take place. The public sector though does not have customers in the traditional sense; instead its role is, as already discussed, to provide quality public services and respond to citizens' and businesses' needs that pertain to a variety of policy domains, including administration, public order and safety, education, health and social care, etc. In this context, the vision of transforming the public sector into technology leader and innovation breeding carrier can only be fulfilled if the potential of emerging ICT technologies and related technological trends is combined with insights on the actual needs of citizens, businesses and public sector constituent organisations.

This is where the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for the Public Sector, a key outcome of the SONNETS project, comes in with the view to couple findings on emerging ICT technologies and technological trends that hold a high innovation potential with insights on current societal challenges and needs, in order to find opportunities for and critically assess the adoption of these technologies in the public sector, as well as to identify appropriate services and applications that may materialise the envisaged innovations. The role and methodological aspects of the SONNETS Framework are analysed at greater detail in the following section.

2.4 The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology

2.4.1 Background

The main aims of SONNETS that have to do with innovation identification and the provision of information and guidance to the public sector to grasp emerging opportunities and become more responsive to future needs, are not radical, as similar discussions and attempts have been recorded in the near past, both in the domain of the public sector (titles as “eGovernment”, “eGovernance” and “Policy Making 2.0” in the past 10 years), but also in the domain of businesses.

In this respect, SONNETS sought to make use of pre-existing knowledge and attempt to port into the project valuable methodological aspects of past attempts, which could prove useful and could accelerate the outputs of the project, given also the limited time of its duration. Out of the ideas transferred into SONNETS, one must mention two past successful projects, Crossroad and FutureEnterprise, which included roadmapping and impact assessment exercises and whose methodological aspects were partially re-used during SONNETS.

In more detail, CROSSROAD “A Participative Roadmap for ICT Research in Electronic Governance and Policy Modelling” with G.A. No FP7-ICT 248484¹, had amongst its core priorities to design a roadmap for Policy Making 2.0, providing also recommendations regarding the uptake of technologies by the Public Sector and the introduction of more collaborative governance models. On the other hand, FuturerEnterprise “Road mapping, Research Coordination and Policy activities supporting Future Internet-based Enterprise Innovation” with G.A. No.611948² had a focus on entrepreneurship and new Business Innovations, examining how enterprises can take advantage of new technologies and of emerging business models.

The consortium had a very clear view of the work methods and the results of those projects as certain partners of SONNETS were involved in those either as members of the core implementation teams, or as external experts that had close collaboration with the aforementioned consortia. In that respect, SONNETS had based parts of its methodology on ideas and methods proposed by those project, and more specifically:

- The “artefact” description methodologies used in CROSSROAD as well as part of the “mutated” SWOT analysis (section 3.5), which inspired the way SONNETS describes technologies and trends.
- The Scenario building exercise of the FutureEnterprise project, which proposed a novel method to draw future scenarios, taking into account the desired and probable futures out of the whole future scenario space.

¹ http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/93842_en.html

² http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/110910_en.html

2.4.2 Overview

The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework is an innovative methodological framework that will accelerate the transformation of the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The goal of the SONNETS Framework is twofold and lies in supporting innovation both **in the public sector** and **through the public sector**.

Figure 2: The goals of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework

Innovation in the public sector may have, as already explained in Section 2.1, an internal or external focus, pertaining to the improvement of the public sector internal processes and the former’s efficiency, and the development of improved services for citizens and businesses respectively, and targets the public sector’s modernization. On the other side, ***innovation through the public sector*** focuses on promoting the generation and implementation of innovative ideas and the corresponding creation of value in other sectors and pursues accordingly the transformation of the public sector into an innovation driver.

The Framework emphasizes the necessity to have an informed view of the current societal trends and challenges as a prerequisite for better accommodating the respective needs, as well as the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) as a key enabler for innovation, and pursues its goal by means of coupling findings on emerging ICTs and trends with insights on current societal challenges and needs. Such coupling is carried out on the basis of specifying and bringing into the foreground specific innovative solutions for the adoption of the identified technologies and the confrontation of the identified needs respectively. In this respect, the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, and more

specifically the innovation solutions specified are considered, as shown in

Figure 3, as the means to bridge the identified needs with technologies.

In the context of the SONNETS project, the identification of needs is the subject of WP2 activities, which pursue to address the question of how societal challenges and public sector needs impact on the former in terms of innovation needs. On the other hand, the identification of technologies constitutes the focus of WP3, which embarks, among others, on specifying applications and services that could benefit from the adoption of the identified technologies under the public sector's umbrella. In this context, the innovation actions specified, make up the point into which the two parallel processes of needs' and technologies' identification converge.

Still, the Framework does not limit its scope in the specification of relevant innovation solutions. It further addresses the assessment and evaluation of their actual innovation potential. The latter is considered under the prism of both the impact and feasibility of the identified solutions. To this end, the Framework defines a set of impact assessment criteria and feasibility assessment criteria, in order to evaluate the innovation potential of the solutions under consideration for the public sector. The former are used to evaluate the magnitude of the potential effects of the identified solutions, whereas the latter are employed to assess the research needs, which the technological, socio-economic and ethical implications of these solutions translate into. The rating of the specified solutions against both the dimensions of impact and feasibility allows distinguishing and, possibly prioritizing, those solutions that hold greater value for the public sector, and lays the foundations for designing a concrete time plan of actions and a set of recommendations for their implementation in practice, i.e. for developing the

SONNETS Roadmap. Both the research needs identification as well as the roadmap design are dealt with under WP4.

Figure 3: The role of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework

From a methodological point of view, the SONNETS Framework relies basically on the methods of desk-based research, interviews, focus groups and workshops, and open consultations, and encompasses six logical steps or phases as follows:

- viii) the identification of societal needs, societal and public sector trends/challenges (needs identification)
- ix) the identification of emerging technologies and trends that make a difference today in other sectors (technology identification)
- x) the analysis of these technologies and trends in terms of their key characteristics and specificities (technology selection and analysis)
- xi) the assessment of these technologies in the domains originally met and their correlation to the public sector needs and societal challenges on the basis of existing services and applications, as well as new innovation solutions that may benefit from these technologies (technology assessment)
- xii) the evaluation of these services' and solutions' innovation potential in terms of both their impact and feasibility (innovation identification)
- xiii) the selection among the former, of those that make more sense to be ported to the public sector through the development of adequate scenarios (scenario building)
- xiv) the evaluation and ratification of the overall findings (results validation)

These discrete but interrelated steps are presented at greater detail in the following sections and correspond to information collection, analysis and evaluation activities which are intended, as shown in Figure 4, to take place in an overlapping way.

Figure 4: Methodology Flow Diagram

The SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework has been used to guide the innovation identification activities within the SONNETS work-plan, but can also be utilised as a self-standing innovation framework for the public sector.

2.5 Stakeholders Involved

SONNETS mission has been to lay the foundations for creating a more productive, responsive and innovation generating public sector, and thereby for addressing the needs of public sector employees and policy makers, but also catering for those of businesses and citizens, so as to develop a win-win situation for all relevant stakeholders. In this respect, it has placed particular emphasis on both identifying and understanding the needs of the former, and taking into consideration their views on the potential of emerging technologies to transform the public sector, as well as on the desired features of new and innovative public sector applications and services.

In this context, the project has pursued not only the dissemination of its research findings to the targeted stakeholders, but also their actual involvement in shaping and validating these findings. In particular, as far as the identification, analysis and evaluation of existing and emerging needs and technologies is concerned, SONNETS has foreseen the engagement of a number of stakeholder groups in various stages of the Innovation Identification Framework Methodology, as follows:

- **Public sector representatives:** SONNETS has targeted primarily public sector institutions, which are eager to transform themselves into technology and innovation generators. Thereby, this group includes representatives of local, regional or central government authorities at national and international level, as well as policy makers and research planners. The latter should be engaged by means of interviews and focus groups or workshops with the view to offer insights on the public sector needs and requirements, discuss the technology and innovation readiness of their organisations and argue with regard to the impact and feasibility of identified innovation solutions.

- IT experts: these should be IT professionals and representatives from all public sector, business, and research domains. IT experts have a leading role when it comes to the adoption of new technologies and trends and thereby they should be engaged in the context of interviews and focus groups with the goal of revealing insights on existing and emerging technologies, assessing their maturity and relevance for the public sector and proposing solutions and applications for their adoption or implementation by the latter.
- Citizen representatives, civil society and the general public: SONNETS pursues the transformation of the public sector in the direction of better responding to society's needs and increasing citizens' trust on public services. In this respect, citizen and civil society representatives should be interviewed in order to offer an insider's perception of the problems and challenges encountered nowadays by citizens, both in the context of their interaction with public authorities, as well as within other aspects of their daily life. Additionally, the promotion of awareness of a wider audience, representing the general public or the society at large, on innovation-driven solutions and initiatives, as well as the former's actual engagement in their validation, should further be pursued by means of online consultations.
- ICT research community, private sector representatives: this group includes ICT research organisations, company, business associations, industry, and not-for-profit organizations representatives that may be interested in SONNETS outcomes, as the latter may be beneficiary for their own research/commercial activities. These should be involved through interviews, focus groups and workshops in the identification of the needs of the private sector, the assessment of strategic technology choices' and trends' potential to cover these needs, as well as the recognition of use cases and best practices that should be considered by the public sector, so as to improve its operation.

Along the course of the project, SONNETS consortium has got in touch with representatives of all of the aforementioned stakeholder groups as per the needs of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology and through the work methods described in detail in the following paragraph.

Additionally, SONNETS partners have worked in close collaboration with the SONNETS Experts Committee, a panel of experts, assembled for the exact purpose of supporting the innovation identification process within SONNETS. The members of the SONNETS Experts Committee have profound knowledge on the operation of the public sector and the use of ICT in its context and have contributed in the innovation identification process as interview partners while also attending the SONNETS events, and in particular the WP3 validation workshop, and participating in a number of follow-up teleconferences as per the needs of the project. These experts have further acted as multipliers to extend the multidisciplinary network of stakeholders and teams, targeted during the project execution. Further to that, the consortium has counted with the support of the SONNETS Expert Advisory Group, a team of external experts willing to

contribute to the project goals, providing feedback on the SONNETS outcomes during the validation workshops to be organized.

Stakeholder Group	Main Focus of Involvement	Methods of involvement
Public sector representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of public sector requirements • Identification of public sector employees' needs • Assessment of the technology and innovation readiness level of public administrations • Assessment of the impact and feasibility of innovation solutions' implementation in the public sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups / or workshops
IT experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of existing and emerging technologies • Assessment of technology maturity • Assessment of technology relevance for the public sector • Suggestion of technological innovation solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups / or workshops
Citizen and civil society representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of citizens' daily life problems and challenges in terms of their interaction with the public sector • Suggestion of innovation solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews
ICT research community and private sector representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of business and industry needs • Assessment of strategic technology choices' and trends' potential to cover the needs of the private sector • Identification of technology use cases and best practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups / or workshops
SONNETS Experts Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of public sector requirements • Identification of business and industry needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups / or workshops

Stakeholder Group	Main Focus of Involvement	Methods of involvement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of technology maturity Suggestion of technological innovation solutions 	
SONNETS Expert Advisory Group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of technological and innovation solutions' proposals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus groups / or workshops
All stakeholders and the general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Awareness promotion on the role of ICT and the innovation potential of ICT solutions) Evaluation of technological and innovation solutions' proposals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online consultation

Table 2: Overview of Stakeholders Engagement

2.6 Innovation Identification Work Methods

The methods to be employed for facilitating the innovation identification process, and thereby for collecting, analysing and evaluating information with regard to societal challenges and public sector needs, as well as emerging technologies and technological trends, include desk-based research, interviews, focus groups, brainstorming and online consultations. A brief description of each method is provided below, along with an explanation on its use in the context of the SONNETS project. Additional information on how these methods map to the methodological steps of the Framework is provided in Section 3.

2.6.1 Desk-based research

Desk-based research, also met as secondary research, is the term used for describing the process of tracking down useful information already available in print or published on the internet. It is concerned with the summary, collation, analysis and/or synthesis of existing knowledge and research, contrary to primary research, in which data are collected from research subjects or experiments [20]. Traditionally using library sources, desk-based research has now largely moved to the internet, leveraging the vast amount of publicly available resources and the latest advances in search engine intelligence. Desk-based research can serve as a stand-alone research technique or as the initial stage of a project and a precursor to primary research.

2.6.1.1 Desk-based research in SONNETS

In the context of the SONNETS project, desk-based research has targeted the identification of societal challenges and public sector needs (as mandated by the work plan of WP2), as well as the identification of emerging technologies and technological trends, along with the potential detection of additional information on these technologies' characteristics in terms of maturity, market potential,

growth, impact etc. (serving the work plan requirements of WP3). The identification of societal and public sector needs has been based upon the examination of a number of sources of information in both the academic and grey literature. On the other hand, the identification of technologies and trends has relied on relevant EC resources, research projects and roadmaps, studies from consultancy firms (e.g. Gartner Hype Cycles, Forrester, Forbes, Deloitte, Accenture, etc. reports), and technology articles, as well as online resources mining algorithms (e.g. Google Trends, 'Research Trends' by Scopus, etc.). The outcomes of desk-based research, i.e. the materials collected, have been used as a pool of preliminary and raw findings, further complemented, reviewed, revised, refined and validated along the course of the project with the help of the work methods exposed in the following paragraphs, i.e. with the help of interviews, focus groups brainstorming and online consultations.

2.6.2 Interviews

An interview is another type of qualitative research, which takes the form of a one-to-one conversation with one person acting in the role of the interviewer and the other in the role of the interviewee, and where questions are asked to elicit information on a specific topic. The main goal of an interview is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say and comprehend their experiences [21]. An interview may take place face-to-face and in person, or online using videoconferencing software.

2.6.2.1 Interviews in SONNETS

In the frame of SONNETS, interviews have taken place with the help of short questionnaires (consisting of no more than 10 questions), on a face-to-face or online communication basis, and have been recorded only upon the interviewee's consent, in the opposite case of which, extensive notes have been taken down.

In particular, two rounds of interviews have been carried out, serving the research requirements of both WP2 and WP3: The first round of interviews has had a focus on needs and pursued the identification of societal and public sector needs, whereas they have involved a number of privileged informants, acting as representatives to the public (public administrations) and enterprise sector (businesses) and the society at large (individuals). The second round of interviews has had instead a technology focus and has targeted the recognition of technologies and trends that are anticipated to have a significant impact for the public sector and its constituent policy domains, whereas they will involve accordingly a number of IT experts, coming from the public sector, the business and research communities. A set of 44 interviews have been conducted in total for these purposes (35 interviews with privileged informants and 11 interviews with IT experts), using the interview guidelines that are incorporated in Appendices A and B of this document.

In spite of the primary goal being in both cases the identification of needs and technologies respectively, these interviews have not limited their scope in a simple enumeration of related items. Instead, as shown through the relevant guidelines, they have pursued to elicit insights on the wider context surrounding the identified needs and technologies. More importantly, in spite of their different focus, they have encouraged interviewees to bring up innovation solutions that

may be implemented to address the identified needs and in parallel apply the identified novel technologies in actual use case settings, thereby contributing into establishing a link among societal and public sector needs and emerging technologies and trends, which make up the two pillars of the Innovation Identification Framework.

2.6.3 Focus groups / Workshops

A focus group is actually a form of qualitative research in which a group of people are asked about their perceptions, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes towards a product, service, concept or idea [22]. Questions are asked in an interactive group setting where, ideally, participants' responses stimulate and influence the thinking and sharing of others. Focus groups can reveal a wealth of detailed information and deep insight. When well executed, a focus group creates an accepting environment that puts participants at ease allowing them to thoughtfully answer questions in their own words and add meaning to their answers [23].

Apparently, conducting a successful focus group requires detailed planning. Factors, such as the number and profile of people to be involved, the duration of the focus group, the number and type of questions to be addressed, as well as the overall planning and conduction of the session are quite critical for its success. A focus group should consist of six to ten people, participating in an open discussion, led by a skilled moderator. The group should be large enough so as to generate ideas and not to limit discussion, but not so large that some participants are left out and voices get lost. Participants should be selected on the basis of specific criteria, i.e. a set of key attributes to possess, established upfront and based on the purpose of the study. On the other side, the ideal amount of time to dedicate to a focus group should be between 45 to 90 minutes. This time frame should be enough to elicit different ideas and opinions from the different people involved, while more than that could possibly lead to unproductive discussions.

The scope of the focus group owes also to be clear and specific, so as to facilitate the rest of the process and the generation of the appropriate questions in particular. The latter have to be carefully selected and formulated. As a focus group is not supposed to last for more than two hours, its time frame should be sufficient for eight to ten questions. This means that only the ones that are really important and qualify for the purpose of the focus group should be included. Questions should further be short and to the point, focused on one dimension each, worded unambiguously and in a way that cannot be answered simply with a "yes" or "no" answer and ordered so as to address issues from the general to the specific. Of course, one or two introductory or warm-up questions could also be included, so as to set the scene for participants.

The selected questions should then form the basis for generating a more detailed script for the focus group, including an opening section to welcome participants, introduce the scope and objectives of the focus group, the questions' part, and a closing section to wrap up the focus group and gather any additional feedback from the participants.

During the focus group session, emphasis should be put on closely monitoring time, so as not to exceed the schedule, and keeping the discussion on track, allowing for all questions to be answered. The role of the facilitator is particularly important during this phase. The latter should be knowledgeable about the project, able to listen attentively, lead discussion, keeping personal views out of it and remaining neutral, cover adequately all prepared questions within the time allotted, and of course get participants to talk and fully explain their answers, making sure that all feel comfortable and that each and every one of them is heard. It is a good practice for the moderator to paraphrase and summarize long, complex or ambiguous comments, as this demonstrates active listening and clarifies the comment for everyone in the group. An assistant facilitator should be present as well, bearing the responsibility of taking notes but also noting and recording body language or other subtle but relevant clues.

After the focus group, the notes and feedback recorded should be transcribed to avoid any memory lapses, summarized and analysed for trending comments and other important elements, such as issues, problems, or questions that arose during the focus group. As a last step, conclusions should be reached, their implications should be discussed and specific actions to address them should be planned.

Practice has shown that usually it takes more than one focus group on the issue of interest to produce valid results, usually at least three or four. A good indication of having conducted enough focus groups would be reaching a point of saturation with regard to the answers/feedback obtained for a particular set of questions.

Overall, the basic steps to plan, carry out and exploit the outcomes of a good focus group could be summarized as follows [24]:

Before the Focus Group

- Define the purpose of the focus group
- Establish the preparatory activities' timeline
- Decide on the number of participants and establish the individuals' participation criteria
- Identify the participants
- Generate the appropriate questions
- Arrange the focus groups logistics (reserve the time and location, plan for food and refreshments, etc.)
- (Invite participants in anticipation of a no-show rate of 10 to 20 percent.)
- Prepare any supportive materials required (list of participants, projection equipment, presentation, notepads and pens, etc.)

During the Focus Group

- Carry out the focus group as per the plan

After the Focus Group

- Transcribe the notes that were taken during the focus group and compile an appropriate summary
- Analyse the focus group data
- Report the focus groups results and translate them into actionable insights

2.6.3.1 Focus groups in SONNETS

In the scope of the SONNETS project, focus groups have either taken the form of closed workshops, organized by the members of the consortium in own premises and engaging selected and predefined participants according to the plan exposed above, or that of open workshops, taking place in the frame of related events or workshops, in which the SONNETS consortium will participate, with the help of semi-structured questionnaires and online polls.

In particular, an introductory focus group with members of the SONNETS Expert Committee has been conducted in M7 of the project to cater for the needs of both WP2 and WP3.

Additionally, four small workshops have taken place within M9 to M10 of the project, in Madrid, Athens, Torino and Cologne, i.e. the cities represented by the consortium members, with the participation and engagement of civil servants and IT representatives of public administrations. These workshops have acted as a means of validating the insights acquired on societal and public sector needs, but also bringing up and discussing the feasibility of appropriate innovation actions and linking the former with specific technologies and trends, thus having a needs' and technologies' orientation at once.

Further to that, in the context of WP3, a validation workshop has also been organised in M12 of the project, in Athens, in order to present and discuss with experts and interested stakeholders the knowledge accumulated around emerging technologies and related innovation solutions. Particular emphasis has been placed in this case in inviting and ensuring the participation of stakeholders with a multidisciplinary background (i.e. representatives of public authorities, civil society organisations, ICT research organisations, companies, etc.). Guidelines on the content of the aforementioned workshops and focus groups can be found in Appendices A and B of this document, as the questionnaires designed to support the conduction of interviews can also be leveraged to encourage discussion in the context of the focus groups to be organized.

2.6.4 Brainstorming and Discussion

Brainstorming stands for the process of generating creative ideas and solutions through intensive discussion. It is a group creativity technique by which efforts are made to find a solution for a specific problem by gathering a list of ideas spontaneously contributed by its members [25]. Every participant is encouraged to think aloud and suggest as many ideas as possible, no matter how outlandish or bizarre they might initially seem. Some of these ideas can be crafted into original, creative solutions to a problem, while others can spark even more ideas [26]. Analysis, discussion, or criticism of the aired ideas is allowed only when the

brainstorming session is over and an evaluation session begins [27]; otherwise it stunts idea generation and limits creativity.

2.6.4.1 Brainstorming in SONNETS

Within SONNETS, brainstorming has been used as a complementary work method, enhancing the consortium attempts towards the identification of innovation solutions, whereas it has also supported the development of hypothetical future scenarios to contextualise and evaluate these solutions.

2.6.5 Online Consultation

The concept of an online consultation pertains in general to using the Internet in order to ask a group of people their opinion on one or more specific topics, allowing for trade-offs between participants [28]. With the rise of the internet popularity with the public as a means of voicing opinion and participating in politics, an online consultation or e-consultation has come to be representative of the exchange that takes place between government and citizens using the internet, as a form of online deliberation: an agency may consult a group of people to get their thoughts on an issue when a project or a policy is being developed or implemented, e.g. to identify or access options, or to evaluate ongoing activities. Through the public engagement attained through an online consultation, government agencies can hold interactive dialogues with the public as they have a more direct route to citizen opinion via the Internet, while they can eventually develop more citizen-centred policies.

2.6.5.1 Online Consultation in SONNETS

In the context of the SONNETS project, the method of online consultation has been employed as a means of validating the research findings of the innovation identification process with the participation of a wide audience of people, representing stakeholders from all the targeted stakeholder groups and especially the general public. In particular, the key takeaways generated with regard to societal and public sector needs have been put on public display through the SONNETS website, and allowing commenting and voting, with the goal of coming up with a prioritization of identified needs and a suggestion of related innovation solutions to address them. The same approach and rationale has further been used to gather feedback and comments around the Innovation Identification Framework itself.

3 Step by Step Methodology

3.1 Overview of the Framework

This section presents an overview of the methodological steps of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, outlining for each step of the process, the work methods employed, the stakeholders involved, the main focus of the activities undertaken and the outputs generated. These steps are exposed at greater detail in the following paragraphs, where along with their description, guidelines for their implementation in practice are provided as well, based on the experience accumulated in the context of the SONNETS project

Step	Work Methods	Stakeholders Involved	Main Focus	Output
i. Needs Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based Research • Interviews • Focus groups 	(Privileged informants) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen representatives • Private sector representatives • Public sector representatives • SONNETS Experts Committee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of societal challenges and citizen needs • Identification of business and industry needs • Identification of public sector needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of Needs
ii. Technology Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based Research • Interviews 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Experts • SONNETS Experts Committee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of existing and emerging technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long list of Technologies
iii. Technology Selection and Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based Research • Interviews • Focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Experts • SONNETS Advisory Group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refinement of the Technology List • Information Collection on the selected existing and emerging technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short list of Technologies • Compendium of Technologies and Trends
iv. Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Experts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft list of potential

Step	Work Methods	Stakeholders Involved	Main Focus	Output
Assessment	Research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews • Focus groups 		impact in other domains <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of technology relevance for the public sector • Interlinking of technologies with relevant needs • Identification of related innovation solutions and interlinking with technologies 	Innovation solutions
v. Innovation Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk-based Research • Interviews • Focus groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT Experts • Public sector representatives • Private sector representatives • ICT research community • SONNETS Experts Committee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of innovation solutions impact for the public sector • Assessment of innovation solutions feasibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation potential records
vi. Scenario Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brainstorming • Discussion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SONNETS Experts Committee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of scenarios for the future of the public sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public sector scenarios
vii. Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop • Online Public Consultation using a Wiki Style portal • Online 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public sector representatives • Civil society representatives • Private sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of feedback and evaluation of findings • Inclusion of new material suggested and loop to step iv for those 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final list of Technologies and selected Innovation solutions

Step	Work Methods	Stakeholders Involved	Main Focus	Output
	Questionnaires	representatives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT research community • The general public • SONNETS Experts Committee • SONNETS Expert Advisory Group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ratification of results 	

Table 3: Overview of the SONNETS Framework Methodology

3.2 Needs Identification

Phase Description

The identification of existing pressing or emerging societal needs, challenges and trends is a key component and prerequisite for delivering innovations that hold true value for the society; thereby, it constitutes the first step and starting point of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology. The latter targets more specifically to identify societal challenges and public sector needs and can be based, given the abstract and wide scope of the subject under study, on qualitative research: the latter should incorporate both a systematic literature review approach, taking into account all relevant research and scientific papers, policy documents, white papers and European Union reports, industry reports, as well as interviews and focus groups with representatives of the stakeholder groups (e.g. citizens, businesses, public sector officials and employees), the needs and requirements of which are to be determined.

These methods are intended to serve as the means to collect but also analyse, prioritize and validate targeted stakeholder needs, and thus generate a list of needs, that can be leveraged in the subsequent steps of the methodology to propose relevant innovation solutions and guide the selection of technologies. Provided that the SONNETS Innovation Framework aims at supporting ICT-driven innovation, attention is drawn to the fact that the latter pertain solely to the ICT domain; therefore the list of needs to be compiled is also to be restricted to needs that can be addressed through the adoption and use of ICT.

Figure 5: Needs identification phase

Proposed Implementation

Based on the experience accumulated in the context of the SONNETS project, needs may be elicited through a deductive, multi-stage process, that targets to

transform an originally collected, wide range of societal needs into a more concrete list of needs that are recognized as priority ones (i.e. needs that need immediate action) by the stakeholders involved and can be addressed through the use of ICT.

This process, that in the frame of the SONNETS workplan has been jointly undertaken by the consortium members and the SONNETS Expert Committee may include primarily the conduction of desk-based research and the subsequent creation of a repository of relevant sources (i.e. academic papers, EU policy documents, industry reports and documents from other EU projects) along with the compilation of a raw, long list of needs and their clustering under broad heading and categories. It may further include the analysis and refinement of the former list by means of interviews with a number of privileged informants, representing individuals, businesses, and the public sector, as well as the identification of top priority needs among them, as stated above, and the generation of a final list of needs. The process may additionally foresee the organization of focus groups as a means of further refining and confirming the generated list of needs, as well as the eventual validation of the latter by means of workshops and online consultations. The needs' identification process, as conducted within the SONNETS project, is described at greater detail in deliverable D2.1.

3.3 Technology Identification

Phase Description

The next step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework Methodology is that of technology identification. This step pertains purely to the conduction of information collection activities, and thereby its nature is a preparatory one, whereas its goal is to provide a pool of emerging technologies and trends that make a difference today in other sectors.

From a methodological point of view, this step relies mainly on extensive desk-based research, and the examination thereby of a variety of information sources, including European Commission resources, research project documents and roadmaps, studies from consultancy firms and online tools, whereas it also encompasses the conduction of interviews with IT experts from the public sector and the business and research communities, as described in Section 2.4 of the present document.

The output of this step, and thus of the aforementioned methods is a preliminary list of technologies and technological trends, being referred to hereinafter as SONNETS long list of technologies, that is to be reviewed and refined during the subsequent steps of the methodology.

Figure 6: Technology Identification phase

Proposed Implementation

Technology identification can be performed both by means of desk-based research and the conduction of interviews with IT experts. Desk-based research may take place in particular under the prism of a crowdsourcing approach, targeting to identify and contribute a notable number of online resources and documents on emerging technologies and trends, towards the creation of a common knowledge base. In this context, preference may be given to reports and testimonials, produced by reliable and credible sources (indicatively Gartner Hype Cycles, IDC, Forrester, Forbes, Deloitte, Accenture, etc. reports), whereas emphasis has to be also placed on the volume of materials, available on the web for each of the identified technologies / trends, in order to drive conclusions on the maturity and popularity of the related terms, and thereby compile a list of well-established and widely accepted technology and trend related terms.

On the other hand, a number of interviews with IT experts, representing the public sector as well as the business and research communities may be conducted, following the interview guidelines, presented in Appendix B and targeting to elicit information on existing and emerging technologies and trends.

3.4 Technology Selection and Analysis

Phase Description

The preliminary list of technologies, generated in the technology identification phase feeds into the next step of the framework methodology, entitled as technology selection and analysis. This step targets to refine the initial list of technologies and trends, based on their relevance for the public sector, and thereby their potential adequacy to fulfil the identified societal and public sector needs, and to go a little deeper with regard to the selected items, and therefore record basic information on them, in order to create a deeper understanding of their characteristics and specificities. Such information needs to include besides the description of the technology’s/trend’s actual scope and application or usage, a note on the application domain, in which the former is originally met, as well as evidence on its anticipated growth and potential in the market.

Figure 7: Technology Selection and Analysis phase

The methods to be employed in the technology selection and analysis phase include the conduction of desk-based research and interviews, as well as the organisation of focus groups, whereas its outcomes can be summarised in the compilation of a refined list of technologies and trends, hereinafter being referred to as *SONNETS short list of technologies* and a *compendium of emerging technologies and trends*, incorporating basic but quite enlightening information on the identified technologies and trends for future reference.

Proposed Implementation

The technology analysis phase may take place, as prescribed in the previous paragraph, by means of desk-based research, interviews and focus groups, engaging stakeholders with a multidisciplinary background. The information to be collected through these methods has to be presented and analysed in a uniform

way (as in in deliverable D3.2), leveraging the template of Appendix C, which incorporates a number of aspects, as follows:

- Identifier: a unique identifier that determines the particular technology (TE#x) or technological trend (TT#x) addressed.
- Type: an indication of whether a technology or trend is a self-standing one or has resulted from the technological convergence of other fields and which these fields are.
- Description: a brief description of the scope, aims and usage of the technology / trend addressed.
- Mainstream Domains of Application: the application domains, in which a technology / trend is basically met.
- Related Market Potential / Forecasted Growth: quantitative (statistic) or qualitative information on the anticipated growth and spread of the technology / trend addressed or the potential and growth of the related market.
- Related Terms: a list of similar terms used to describe the particular technology / trend or to denote specific aspects of it, and that can be employed to collect further information.
- Source(s): a reference to the source(s), drawing attention to or pointing out the particular technology / trend as an important one for the years to come.

3.5 Technology Assessment

Phase Description

The fourth step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Methodology maps to technology assessment. This step is intended to dive even deeper with regard to the analysis of the identified technologies and trends, targeting on the one side to assess the impact of the former in the domains basically met, and to draw conclusions, on the other, with regard to their relevance for the public sector, and the different policy domains.

Apparently, this phase is meant to use as input both the long list and compendium of technologies as well as the confirmed and validated set of societal and public sector needs, whereas it will employ the same arsenal of methods, namely desk-based research, interviews and focus groups that are prescribed in Section 2.4 of this document. On the other hand, as an outcome, it will deliver the technology SWOT analysis and a draft, preliminary list of potential innovation solutions.

Figure 8: Technology Assessment

Proposed Implementation

Technology assessment can be supported, as described above, through desk-based research, interviews and focus groups, facilitating the collection and analysis of information and feedback on the impact of the identified technologies in the domains basically met, as well as on their relevance for the public sector and the different policy domains. Technology assessment can more specifically be grounded on a SWOT approach. The latter may be an adapted SWOT analysis, using the “Strengths” and “Weaknesses” components of the SWOT matrix to identify the impact, namely the benefits and weak points, of each identified technology / trend in the domain originally met, and the “Opportunities” and “Threats” blocks to draw high level correlations among the considered technologies and trends and the opportunities of their adoption, usage and promotion by the public sector as well as the imposed challenges and threats, and thereby to provide raw evidence on whether their adoption by the latter is attainable and meaningful.

Conclusions can then be based upon these preliminary correlations, as well as on matching technologies and trends with identified challenges and needs. On another level, technology assessment may further rely on bringing up existing applications and services that may benefit from the adoption and further evolution of the investigated trends and technologies under the public sector’s umbrella, as well as on conceptualising new and innovative services and applications that have the potential to materialize the envisaged benefits. Overall, the linking of identified technologies and trends to the public sector and other policy domains may take place along three levels, these of the SWOT analysis identifying opportunities and threats, the correlation with specific needs and the identification of existing or new services.

The materials collected during this phase have to be accordingly presented and analysed in a uniform way (as in deliverable D3.2), leveraging the template of Appendix D, which incorporates a number of aspects, as follows:

- Identifier: a unique identifier that determines the particular technology or technological trend addressed (same as in the technology analysis phase).
- SWOT Analysis: an adapted, as described above, SWOT analysis, using the “Strengths” and “Weaknesses” components of the SWOT matrix to identify the impact, namely the benefits and weak points, of each identified technology / trend in the domain originally met, and the “Opportunities” and “Threats” blocks to draw high level correlations among the considered technologies and trends and the opportunities of their adoption, usage and promotion by the public sector as well as the imposed challenges and threats.
- Relevant Needs: a list of the societal needs that may be associated with the particular technology or trend.
- Potential Applications / Services: a list of existing or new services that may materialise the envisaged innovations.
- Existing solutions / products / services: a list of established solutions or best practices based on the specific technology or trend.

Based on the former aspects, the relevance of the identified technologies and trends to the public sector and other policy domains may take place along three levels, these of the SWOT analysis identifying opportunities and threats, the correlation with specific needs and the identification of existing or new services.

3.6 Innovation Identification

Phase Description

The fifth step of the Framework Methodology pertains to technology identification and constitutes a key task in the process of transforming the public sector into an innovation breeding carrier. The focus during this step transposes from the level of technologies to the level of the innovation solutions identified and the goal is to come up with a systematic way to record and assess the innovation potential of these solutions. The latter has to be evaluated in particular against the dimensions of both the impact and feasibility of the identified solutions, thus calling for the determination and consideration of appropriate assessment criteria.

As far as the impact assessment component is concerned, such criteria need to capture the potential scope of application, the type and quality of influence of the identified solutions and technologies against a number of innovation dimensions, related to the public sector and other policy domains, whereas on the side of the feasibility assessment component, such criteria have to take into account aspects, such as the existing ICT infrastructure and know-how, the status of the related legislative framework and regulation, the readiness of the stakeholders involved, as well as the political will demonstrated in the specific application context.

The innovation identification employs as well the methods of interviews and focus groups primarily and desk-based research secondarily in order to collect and analyse information on the innovation potential of the identified solutions, while as an output it produces a *set of appropriate records*.

Figure 9: Innovation Identification phase

Proposed Implementation

Innovation identification may rely on the aforementioned methods and follow a structured approach which takes into account the goals of the Innovation Identification Framework and involves a number of assessment dimensions. The innovation potential of the identified technologies and trends may accrue more specifically as the resultant of two basic components, namely the impact and feasibility of the identified technology solutions. The latter are to be qualitatively assessed against a number of appropriate impact and feasibility assessment dimensions, which are detailed in the following paragraphs. The assessment performed can be based on the consideration and assessment of the materials produced during the previous step of the Framework, namely the SWOT analysis and list of potential innovation solutions, whereas it may also leverage insights from the materials collected through all desk-based research, interviews with IT experts and focus groups/workshops. The outcome of this step shall be, as already suggested, a set of “innovation records”, appropriate for future reference.

Component I - Impact Assessment

As far as the impact component is concerned, a number of vertical dimensions are recognised. These pertain in the case of public sector modernization to the institutional or capacity development and political domains (see Figure 10: “Public Sector Modernization” Impact Assessment Areas), whereas as far as the goal of transforming the public sector into an innovation driver is concerned, these enumerate key policy domains, i.e. the economic, social, infrastructural/transport

and environmental domains (as shown in Figure 11: “Public Sector as an Innovation Driver” Impact Assessment Areas). Each of these domains is further being analysed accordingly in a number of lesser aspects, which map to the specific directions where the impact of the identified ICT solutions can be located. The selection of these aspects is justified in the following paragraphs.

Figure 10: “Public Sector Modernization” Impact Assessment Areas

(I) PS Modernization

➤ Institutional/ Capacity Development

- Degree of Resources (Capital, Personnel, Infrastructure) Utilization: ICTs can be used to reduce or optimize the use of another resource by a process. Such resource may be labour, capital or a natural resource (e.g. energy), i.e. some material resource. Thereby, the use of ICTs in the public sector to improve the former’s operation and processes, and in this respect ICT-driven process optimization, can be seen as substituting technological knowhow (immaterial resource) and/or infrastructure (material resource) for other material resources, thus reducing the amount of resources required and/or intensifying their use.
- Efficiency / Productivity: ICTs play indisputably a major role in the improvement of public sector efficiency and productivity, as they are qualified as general purpose technologies, i.e. technologies that are pervasive and can thus be applied to several production sectors³. As a result, their impact on the

³ Federico Biagi (2013). ICT and Productivity: A Review of the Literature – JRC Technical Reports. Available from <http://ftp.jrc.es/EURdoc/JRC84470.pdf>

former dimensions has to be taken into account, though it may be difficult to be determined, due to the nature of the public sector operation, which is process-based, the nature of the outcomes produced (services, intangibles, often unpriced or collectively consumed), their heterogeneity, as well as due to the multiple levels of focus (e.g. government wide level, sectoral level, individual organization level) to be potentially considered.

- Sustainability: Sustainability is a direct outcome of the operation of the public sector in a way that guarantees proper fulfilment of both present and future needs. As such it is indirectly influenced by the introduction and usage of modern ICTs in view of achieving efficiency and productivity gains, ensuring optimization of the resources available and providing high quality services, as well as by the necessary provisions for their maintenance and updating.
- Cross-organization Cooperation: The purpose of implementing e-Governance (which stands for the application of ICTs in government processes), is to improve governance processes and outcomes with the view to improving the delivery of public services. Thereby, the quality of services offered to citizens and businesses is an important dimension of the technology impact assessment analysis. Improvements in the quality of public services as a result of the introduction of ICTs may take several forms, including the reduction of personal interface of citizens and businesses with public service providers or the increase in the speed of response, and the generation thus of time savings, the reduction of bureaucratic red tape and the corresponding simplification of relevant processes, the increase in the availability of public services, as well as their delivery through additional channels.
- Quality of Services Provided: In order to be effective and efficient but also to deliver citizens and businesses quality public services, public sector authorities cannot operate today isolated but need to establish cooperation among each other. ICT is a necessary condition for such cooperation, which concerns both the different levels of public administration, e.g. local, regional, national etc. as well as diverse policy domains of the same administrative level. Such cooperation further applies at the European level with the view of providing cross-border public services, supporting the rights of citizens to live and work anywhere in the Union and of businesses to offer services across the EU single market.
- Image Modernization: The image and public standing of an organization plays inevitably a major role in target audience preferences and thereby in the outcomes of the technology impact assessment analysis. Attention has to be drawn to the

fact that the image of an institution is a rather elusive topic, as there is virtually no comparative research as to the level of the institution's public standing. On the other hand, the institutional quality control processes differ immensely across public sector organizations and offer no guarantee of raising public standing. As this is nevertheless a vital aspect of institutional development, it has to be considered as a facet of impact assessment.

➤ Political

- Level of Participation: Information and communication technologies can facilitate democratic processes and increase the participation of citizens in these. Such impacts may occur as a result of greater communication and information dissemination offered by ICTs, through the use of social networking sites, e-mail and mobile phones. They are also frequently enabled by electronic information and services offered by government (e-government). Of particular interest is additionally how e-government can improve democratic processes and encourage citizen participation in decision-making and how e-participation in specific can change the dynamics between government and citizens⁴.
- Transparency: ICT constitutes the main lever of e-government, which contributes in turn to enhancing accountability and promoting good governance in the public sector, which are thus taken as an assessment dimension under the aspect of Transparency.
- Creation of Trust & Confidence: Trust is a complex interpersonal and organizational construct⁵. In political terms, trust means that citizens appraise the government and its institutions, policy-making in general and/or the individual political leaders as promise-keeping, efficient, fair and honest⁶. Political trust, in other words, is the "judgment of the citizenry that the system and the political incumbents are responsive, and will do what is right even in the absence of constant scrutiny"⁷. Citizens' trust and confidence in government is influenced by several factors, including citizens' satisfaction and expectations, transparency, accountability, digital transformation of government and

⁴ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dtlstict2011d1_en.pdf

⁵ Duck, S. The Handbook of Personal Relationships: Theory, Research and Interventions. New York: Wiley, 1997.

⁶ Blind, P.K. (2006). Building Trust in Government in the twenty-first century: Review of Literature and Emerging Issues, UNDESA.

⁷ Miller, A. H. and O. Listhaug. "Political Parties and Confidence in Government: A Comparison of Norway, Sweden and the United States," British Journal of Political Science 20, 3 (July 1990): 357-386.

performance of the government⁸, all either directly or indirectly affected notably by the introduction and usage of ICTs.

Figure 11: "Public Sector as an Innovation Driver" Impact Assessment Areas

(II) PS as an Innovation Driver

➤ Economical

- Productivity (Labour / Capital / Resource) & Growth: The impact of ICT on economic growth and productivity can be considered at the macro, sectoral and firm levels. At the microeconomic level, positive impacts of ICT can be attributed to i. the increase in the size and productivity of the ICT sector, and associated effects such as growth in industries that provide inputs to ICT production, ii. ICT investment across the economy, which contributes to capital deepening and leads to a rise in labour productivity, iii. multi-factor productivity growth across the economy, which arises from the role of ICT in helping firms innovate and improve their overall efficiency^{9,10}. Macro-level research has generally shown a positive link between ICT investment and growth in GDP¹¹. A growing ICT sector (ICT services and ICT manufacturing industries) can contribute to aggregate increases in productivity, GDP and trade. Opportunities for economic growth arise also for businesses retailing ICT goods. Enterprises in other sectors as well may benefit from the use of more sophisticated ICT applications (such as web-based e-commerce and other e-business applications). There may also be spillover benefits. For instance, ICT investment in a larger enterprise may benefit a whole sector, whereas there may furthermore be gains from ICT

⁸ Mohamed, M. (2016). Enhancing Citizens' Trust and Confidence in Government through Digital Transformation, in IJEGR, 12(1), IGI Global.

⁹ OECD (2004). The Economic Impact of ICT, Measurement, Evidence and Implications. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/bookshop/pub=922004051P1>

¹⁰ OECD (2008). The Contribution of the ICT Sectors to Economic Growth in OECD Countries: Backward and Forward Linkages. DSTI/ICCP/IIS(2008)2.

¹¹ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dt1stict2011d1_en.pdf

diffusion along the supply chain. At the firm level use of computers, the Internet and broadband have a positive relationship with productivity. However, this varies among individual businesses according to other factors, such as skills and innovation. A particular challenge of firm level studies is measuring the effect of intangibles, such as good management and marketing¹². A number of studies have found that ICT has most impact when accompanied by complementary investments and changes, for example, in human capital, organizational change and other forms of innovation¹³.

There is further some evidence that the development of a strong ICT sector can lead to poverty alleviation, although there are few targeted studies on this¹⁴. The concept of poverty though extends beyond the economic dimension and can be considered along its social dimension under the aspect of well-being and prosperity. Negative economic impacts associated with ICT diffusion have received relatively little attention from statisticians. A possible indirect negative impact is a productivity trap resulting from updating ICT too frequently to enable efficiency gains.

- Entrepreneurship: The value of ICT extends far beyond direct economic benefits. ICT is a driving force in the acceleration of entrepreneurship, making it easier to identify and develop good ideas, and create and disseminate new products and services. Some of the ways in which ICT supports entrepreneurship include increasing interconnectedness and collaboration, allowing smaller, entrepreneurship companies to compete in global markets, lowering the cost of entry for new entrepreneurs, facilitating research diversification and interdisciplinary approaches, enhancing the ability of entrepreneurs to develop new business models, products, services and processes, shortening product development cycles, providing new tools to create, organize, store and transmit information, supporting disruptive business models that transform industries and enabling faster access to regional and international markets¹⁵.
- Innovation: Innovation is a broad concept, defined by the Oslo Manual¹⁶ as “the implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organizational method in business

¹² UNCTAD (2007). Information Economy Report 2007–2008: Science and Technology for Development, the New Paradigm of ICT. United Nations. New York and Geneva. Available from http://unctad.org/en/docs/sdteecb20071_en.pdf

¹³ OECD (2004). The Economic Impact of ICT, Measurement, Evidence and Implications. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/bookshop?pub=922004051P1>

¹⁴ UNCTAD (2010). Information Economy Report 2010: ICTs, Enterprises and Poverty Alleviation. United Nations. New York and Geneva. Available from <http://www.unctad.org/ier2010>

¹⁵ Intel (2011). The Path to Growth: Accelerating Entrepreneurship and Innovation Through ICT. Available at: <http://www.intel.com/content/dam/www/public/us/en/documents/white-papers/world-ahead-accelerating-entrepreneurship-paper.pdf>

¹⁶ OECD and Eurostat (2005). Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data. Third Edition. Available from <http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/download/9205111e.pdf?expires=1472036902&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=595B614F50153D1656E1EA1160FE6E58>

practices, workplace organization or external relations”. Innovation can occur in all sectors of the economy, including government and higher education, and involves all forms of research and experimental development, as defined by the Frascati Manual¹⁷. ICT is widely recognized as a major enabler of innovation: according to a study by OECD, higher ICT use, as measured by the number of web facilities, generally increases the probability of innovation¹⁸. Thereby innovation is an important impact assessment dimension.

- Employment: ICTs have undoubtedly a role in the creation of employment and self-employment opportunities¹⁹. Impacts of ICTs’ and related trends’ adoption can be direct through growth of the ICT sector and ICT-using industries and indirect through multiplier effects. In economies dependent on ICT, individuals can benefit by having requisite ICT skills, thereby enhancing their opportunities for employment. Arguably, ICT can also lead to loss of employment as a result of task automation.

➤ Social

- Prosperity & Well-being: The consideration of prosperity and well-being as a dimension of impact assessment can be justified by the ICT impacts identified in the fields of poverty alleviation and employment under the economical domain and the field of healthcare quality under the social domain.
- Quality of Education: ICTs may deliver significant educational benefits by providing tools for improving the teaching and learning process. Other possible impacts of ICT in education are improved attitudes to learning, development of teachers’ technology skills and increased access of the community to adult education and literacy^{20, 21}, which all potentially raise the quality level of education.
- Quality of Health: Quality of Health is also brought forward as an area, where ICT is expected to bring major benefits.

¹⁷ OECD (2002). Frascati Manual: Proposed Standard Practice for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development. Available from <http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/docserver/download/9202081e.pdf?expires=1472037200&id=id&accname=guest&checksum=062653253D1CC67C0DEA522B04BA02AA>

¹⁸ OECD (2010) Are ICT Users More Innovative? An Analysis of ICT-enabled Innovation in OECD Firms. Available from http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/economics/are-ict-users-more-innovative_eco_studies-2011-5kg2d2hkn6vq?crawler=true

¹⁹ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dt1stict2011d1_en.pdf

²⁰ OECD (2010). Are the New Millennium Learners Making the Grade? Technology Use and Educational Performance in PISA. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/edu/cei/45053490.pdf>

²¹ Kozma RB (2005). Monitoring and Evaluation of ICT for Education Impact: A Review. In: Wagner DA et al., eds. Monitoring and Evaluation of ICT in Education Projects: A Handbook for Developing Countries. infoDev. Available from https://www.infodiv.org/infodiv-files/resource/InfodivDocuments_284.pdf

According to the World Health Organization²², e-health, broadly defined as “the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) for health”, targets to “improve health by enhancing patient services and health systems”. According to ITU²³, e-health applications include electronic health records, e-telemedicine, m-health (the use of mobile devices such as mobile phones for health purposes), decision-support systems, e-learning and e-journals. OECD²⁴ also cites the use of ICT as enabling complex and networked equipment. The application of ICT in health holds major benefits for provider organizations, patients and medical staff, and thus enhances the quality of healthcare provision. On the other hand, there is no doubt that ICT can also have negative effects on health, for instance, occupational overuse injuries associated with computer use.

- Equity & Inclusiveness: The ease and immediacy of communicating, finding information and accessing services, offered by ICTs, creates particularly beneficial impacts for minority groups and those who are socially disadvantaged²⁵, thus catering for improved equity and inclusiveness within the social domain.
- Privacy & Security: The effects of ICTs on the privacy and security of individuals and organizations are positive only to the point that the solutions adopted are invulnerable to malicious physical or cyberspace attacks. From that point on, there is a number of adverse impacts, such as commercial losses from denial of service attacks, data loss through theft or corruption and disclosure of confidential data. Far more serious potential negative impacts may arise because of the increasing reliance of critical infrastructure on ICT and the serious consequences of failure²⁶. Hence, privacy and security is a significant dimension of impact assessment.

➤ **Infrastructural**

- Public Safety: Public safety involves “the prevention of and protection from events that could endanger the safety of the general public by means of significant danger, injury/harm, or property damage, such as crimes or disasters (natural or

²² WHO (2009). Global Observatory for eHealth 2009 Survey. Available from http://www.who.int/goe/data/global_e-health_survey_2009_en.pdf

²³ ITU (2010). World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report 2010: Monitoring the WSIS Target – A mid-term review. Available from http://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-d/opb/ind/D-IND-WTDR-2010-PDF-E.pdf

²⁴ OECD (2007). Measuring the Impacts of ICT Using Official Statistics. Working Party on Indicators for the Information Society. DSTI/ICCP/IIS(2007)1/FINAL. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/dataoecd/43/25/39869939.pdf>

²⁵ UNCTAD (2011). Measuring the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology for Development. UNCTAD Current Studies on Science, Technology and Innovation. N ° 3 Available from http://unctad.org/en/Docs/dt1stict2011d1_en.pdf

²⁶ OECD (2008). Shaping Policies for the Future of the Internet Economy. OECD Ministerial Meeting on the Future of the Internet Economy, Seoul, 2008. Available from <http://www.oecd.org/internet/ieconomy/40821707.pdf>

human-made²⁷. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have always played an important role in the public safety domain, providing support in all phases of disaster management, e.g. in preparation, mitigation, response or recovery. The impacts of the use of ICTs on public safety have more specifically to be sought in the directions of enabling effective management of rescue operations, improving the coordination of human and technical resources, reducing the speed of reactions, supporting the mobility of public safety officers and first responders and providing an accurate view of the circumstances.

- Transport Infrastructure: Information and Communication Technology is rapidly evolving and taking centre stage in every domain of everyday life. The same applies for the transport domain, where ICT is greatly influencing mobility and travel choices, as well as travel experience, attempting to provide safer, smarter and greener transport options, improve transport services and design better transport policies.
 - ICT Infrastructure: The ICT infrastructure of the public sector is apparently an aspect, directly influenced by the introduction and adoption of new technologies. Every investment performed by the public sector enhances its ICT infrastructure and potentially creates the conditions for the development of more powerful applications and enhanced services.
 - e-Security: While there are countless benefits associated with the introduction and use of Information and Communication Technologies, there is a down side too. The task of protection of the data and information stored in computers and travelling across the internet has never been so challenging. E-security therefore constitutes a specialized area within the technology impact assessment analysis, which points out that it is not sufficient to adopt and deploy new technologies, but effort has to be placed as well into making the relevant services reliable and secure.
- Environmental
- Quality of the Biosphere: The identification of the impacts of ICT on the environment and the quality of the biosphere in particular is a relatively new topic. According to OECD²⁸ positive impacts enumerate the facilitation of dematerialization, whereas negatives account for an increased dependence on electrical and other forms of energy.

²⁷ Wikipedia – Public safety organizations, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_safety_organizations

²⁸ OECD (2009). Measuring the Relationship between ICT and the Environment. Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/internet/ieconomy/43539507.pdf>

- Environmental Awareness Creation: The role of ICT on the creation of environmental awareness can only be positive and includes ICT's contribution in climate change monitoring and modelling, the dissemination of information, as well as the administration of carbon-pollution-reduction schemes.

These make up, as already explained, a number of vertical dimensions and are further complemented, as shown in Figure 12 by a set of horizontal impact assessment dimensions, referring to the extent of application of the identified technology solutions, therefore to whether the former can be applied at the individual, local, regional, national or international level, and to their anticipated influence, the latter being characterised by its type (direct, indirect or non-existent) and its (positive or negative) quality.

Figure 12: Overview of Impact and Feasibility Assessment Dimensions

Component II - Feasibility Assessment

On the side of the feasibility, the assessment analysis takes into account aspects such as the existing ICT infrastructure and know-how, the status of the related legislative framework and regulation, the readiness of the stakeholders involved, as well as the political will demonstrated in the specific application **context**. This assessment tries to evaluate the identified solutions against these aspects on an appropriate qualitative scale, as follows:

- Existing Infrastructure
 - Inadequate
 - Sufficient
 - Complete
- Legislative framework and regulation
 - Inadequate
 - With Shortcomings

- Sufficient
- Stakeholder IT literacy
 - Low
 - Moderate
 - High
- Political Will
 - Inadequate commitment
 - Strong commitment

Attention is drawn to the fact that the conduction of the feasibility assessment analysis as prescribed above, presupposes having a thorough knowledge of the context (local, regional, national or international), in which the application of the identified technology solutions is meant to take place, in order to generate meaningful results. Thereby, in the context of the SONNETS project and for the sake of completeness, the feasibility assessment is performed as an academic exercise for selected innovation solutions, each evaluated against the country context (Germany, Greece, Italy, Spain) represented by each of the SONNETS partners.

3.7 Scenario Building

Phase Description

The scenario building phase is meant to set the scene for the application of the identified solutions through the development of a series of hypothetical future scenarios that will guide the selection of those solutions among them that make more sense to be ported into the public sector.

A scenario is to be intended as a systematic vision of future possibilities²⁹. Conducting such a foresight research usually means both plausible possibilities as well as others that do not rely on too extreme wild cards. They are used as tools for political or strategic decision-making and to explore the impact of particular decisions or developments in the future³⁰. More specifically, Scenario Building aims to identify uncertain developments in the future and take those uncertainties as elements of the scenario narrative.

This step is anticipated to use as input the previously generated innovation potential records and to leverage brainstorming techniques in order to develop scenarios on the future of the public sector. The selection of the solutions and therefore the technologies that the public sector needs to adopt can then be based on the specification of the most desired and most probable public sector future scenarios.

Figure 13: Scenario Building phase

²⁹ Janssen, M., Duin, P. van der, Wagenaar, R., Blicking, M., Wimmer, M. (2007) Scenario building for e-government in 2020, ACM Proceedings of the 8th annual international conference on Digital government research: bridging disciplines & domains, pp 296 – 297

³⁰ Nekkers, J. (2007) Wijzer in de toekomst: werken met toekomstscenario's. Business Contact.

Proposed Implementation

Regarding the conceptual framework that aims to formulate the visionary scenario exercise, it has to be noted that foresight research comprises many different methods that can be categorised in several ways. According to the classification introduced by Popper³¹, one may distinguish between a methods' orientation (normative or exploratory), its nature (quantitative or qualitative) and its essence (expert-based, creativity-based, interaction-based or evidence-based) as shown in the following figure.

Figure 14: Foresight methods classified by their essence (source: Popper, 2008)

In general, the objectives of a foresight exercise and the degree of uncertainty and complexity involved, are the ones that usually guide the selection of methods for each exercise.

The aim of the scenario building activities is to explore different possible alternative futures regarding the role of the Public Sector in relation to Innovation and Societal Challenges tackling.

For the given topic, both the selected time horizon of this exercise and the interrelationships of different developments affecting it (like rapid ICT developments) make the future quite dynamic, complex and uncertain, with little available evidence that can be used to predict or forecast those futures. Given this lack of evidence and data, it is impossible to use quantitative and evidence-based methods. Courtney et al³² describe this amount and type of uncertainty as a 'level 3', at which a range of different possible futures can be identified, and point 3 types of foresight methods able to accommodate this level: scenario

³¹ Popper, R. (2008) Foresight methodology. In Eds Georghiou, L, Cassingena, J., Keenan, M., Miles, I., Popper, R. The handbook of technology foresight. Edward Elgar Publishing

³² Courtney, H., Kirkland, J., and Viguerie, P. (1997) Strategy under uncertainty, Harvard Business Review, 67–79.

drafting, back casting and early warnings systems. As the latter two approaches are often incorporated into scenario drafting, the method of scenario design has been suggested for the SONNETS framework³³.

The overall working method suggested takes inspiration and is founded on past scenario building exercises of similar context, which were performed in the past in EC cofounded projects such as FutureEnterprise and CROSSROAD, and the overall methodological approach, that is presented in Figure 15: Extreme Points in a 3D Scenario Space, and is as follows:

1. Analysis of the technologies and trends documented in the previous steps of the framework for determining the developments that can be considered key drivers for the future.
2. Selection of main Key Uncertainties whose realisation will drive the Public Sector to different futures.
3. Conduction of an open crowdsourcing exercise to get feedback regarding the Key Uncertainties with a view on what is probable to happen and on what is desirable to happen.
4. Elaboration of the different factors and of the role of the Public Sector in those scenarios through a dedicated brainstorming session.
5. Drafting the scenarios based on the results acquired from the previous step which denoted the different socioeconomic factors and business related aspects of the future.

Scenario building exercises focus in most of the cases on identifying extreme futures based on a limited set of uncertainty factors. Those are being documented in most of the cases as combinations of different Key Uncertainties, usually into groups of 2 (or in some rare case 3)) which can be graphically represented as vertical axes constructing a two-dimensional area (or a cube, forming a 3-dimensional space in the case of 3 Key Uncertainties).

Figure 15: Extreme Points in a 3D Scenario Space

As such, scenario-building exercises aim to describe extreme future situations that may become a reality if the world follows the path towards these endpoints. The different extreme Scenarios are set on the edges of the defined space and

³³ Scenario writing is a method that is commonly used in research regarding public services and eGovernment (Duin, van der & Huijboom, 2008; Janssen et. al., 2007; Aicholzer, 2005)

they describe the conditions that will dominate in such a future (on each of the Key Uncertainties identified above).

Even though, this approach is used extensively in various roadmapping exercises (of which the scenario building constitutes an interim step), there are two major weaknesses that have been criticised in the past that have to do a) with the number of key uncertainties as most exercises tend to overdo it, and b) with the overall approach of investigating these scenarios.

With regard to point a), the project suggest to select various combinations of 2 or at maximum 3 uncertainties, both for reasons of processing, but also for reasons of comprehension, as more than 3 axes are very difficult to be displayed, processed and easily communicated to stakeholders. Such a proposal, is not only limiting the degree of complexity, but also the possibilities to generate unrealistic scenarios (which come as combination of extremes of different axes).

Furthermore, regarding point b), it is noted that the investigation of the extreme points does not offer the expected added value needed to carry on with the definition of the actions required to move forwards, as such extreme situations are highly unrealistic (or too futuristic) and have a relatively low realisation probability. Thus, describing such scenarios does not evidently lead to a set of gaps (which are then transformed into action lines in a roadmap) that stand between the as-is and the to-be situation. This is simply because the unanimously desirable future scenario is not placed on the table, due to the binary logic of these frameworks which focus only on extreme future situations.

SONNETS has tried to differentiate itself from this complex approach by adopting a method that is able to take into consideration different Key Uncertainties and then limit down the analysis to the most realistic scenarios. As such, the methodology sequentially has tried to investigate the different Probable and Desirable scenarios (coming through a crowdsourced exercise, and therefore not being polarised by experts' opinions). As such, not every possible combination of the selected Key Uncertainties has been examined (as this would generate a huge number of scenarios) but focus has been placed on what is most likely to happen (Probable Scenarios), and on what seems like an ideal future (Desirable Scenario).

Investigating those different sets (see Figure 16), has helped to formulate more realistic propositions towards the domain's stakeholders. These may not only uncover future opportunities, but showcase also potential actions that need to be performed to cater for sustainable investments, identifying the shifts that will most likely (need to) happen in the quest of the world becoming a place which is more productive, sustainable and nice to live and work in. In this context, once these scenarios are defined, attention should be turned into the necessary actions that will bring the probable future as close as possible to the desirable one.

Figure 16: Probable Futures and the Desirable one

With regards to the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, four Key Uncertainties are proposed, which may be selected for building the different scenarios. These Key Uncertainties do not claim to cover the entire landscape of the future regarding the role of the Public Sector inside an ICT-powered society, but can be taken as a core material to base the main assumption of the different scenarios. As such, they can be complemented with other Key Uncertainties, replaced or disregarded, depending on the context of each application of the framework.

Public Sector Role	Urgency of Societal Needs	Degree of Power Concentration	Operations & Decision Making
Innovation Leader	Prosperity	Centralised Governance	Machine Intelligence
Open Innovation Evangelist	Stability	Hybrid Decision Structures	Knowledge based
Innovation Facilitator	Scarcity	Federated Decision Systems	Crowd Wisdom

Table 4: SONNETS Scenarios Key Uncertainties and Possible Values

The following lines present very briefly the conditions that correspond to each value of the key uncertainties presented above.

- **Key Uncertainty I – Public Sector Role**
 - Innovation Leader. The Public sector is fully modernized, assets are generally openly exposed, PPPs with third party stakeholders are established, big governmental labs push technology, selected population groups are testing novel techs and innovations, intense collaboration with industry, startups and entrepreneurs is taking place.
 - Open Innovation Evangelist. There is a highly modernised Public Sector, novel technologies are adopted soon after they go mainstream, selected assets are openly provided to the public, close collaboration with industry and few enterprises takes place.
 - Innovation Facilitator. Public sector is still a technology laggard, innovations are adopted after widespread adoption and there is a high demand pressure from the public.
- **Key Uncertainty II – Urgency of Societal Needs**
 - Prosperity. Most Needs solved, Fast growth, Natural & human resources in abundance, high average per capita income, fair distribution of wealth, high life expectancy, highly educated societies, long peace.
 - Stability. A 2-speed world with economic, socio-political and environmental sustainability, mix of social classes, average income distribution, micro-conflicts.
 - Scarcity. Societal Needs are still not tackled, shortage of resources, high levels of inequality in income, education and health, polarised social classes, frequent signs of upheaval (riots, medium to high-intensity conflicts).
- **Key Uncertainty III - Degree of Power Concentration**
 - Centralised Governance. Decisions are taken centrally, and management is performed centrally too, leaving no flexibility to grassroots movements and individual innovation.
 - Hybrid Decision Structures. Collaboration between central and federated decision makers, knowhow transfer, leaving central and more strategic decisions to central authorities and implementation to smaller scale organisations, better openness.
 - Federated Decision Systems. Local decisions, smaller scale impact, less openness, competition between federations, innovation silos.
- **Key Uncertainty IV - Operations & Decision Making**
 - Machine Intelligence. Management, operational processes, supporting activities & external communication are based exclusively on machines (Artificial Intelligence and Automation).
 - Knowledge based. Machine-intensive operational and supporting processes, controlled and managed by human intelligence.
 - Crowd Wisdom. Decisions are taken through crowdsourcing and collaboration of community members, tradition plays an important role into making choices, and technology performs only transactional and heavy-duty operations.

3.8 Validation

Phase Description

The refined list of innovation solutions and respective technologies, as reflected through the appropriate developed scenarios will eventually provide input for the last step of the framework methodology, targeting the validation of the overall findings. The latter is intended to place these findings under evaluation in order to gather feedback, revise and validate the results. Evaluation and validation in this context are to be performed through specialized workshops, engaging representatives of public authorities, civil society organizations, research institutes and companies, and online public consultations, engaging the general public, as well as online questionnaires. Regarding online consultation, the use of wiki-like tools is promoted in order to foster collaborative commenting and co-authoring of sections which need to be improved and revised.

Figure 17: Validation phase

Proposed Implementation

Validation of the findings may be pursued in line with the description of the particular step of methodology, i.e. by coupling offline validation with online feedback, through the organisation of physical workshops and online consultation activities respectively.

Initially, during this step a detailed time plan for the evaluation activities is devised, allocating enough time to perform corrective actions, as well as include new knowledge to the whole process, by looping back to step iv. Of the methodology. Such a time plan should include the following steps, which should be executed sequentially.:

1. Online validation Activities based on a consultation toolkit (e.g. CommentPress³⁴). This will allow the project team to gather feedback and perform corrective actions as needed, while the feedback to be received. Such an activity may be carried out with the view to allow interested stakeholders and the general public to vote and comment on findings with regard to societal and public sector needs and emerging technologies and trends. For more information, the reader may consult the online consultation that has been organised in the context of the SONNETS project and which is accessible at <http://www.sonnets-project.eu/content/online-consultation>.
2. Online Survey through Online Questionnaires. This step comes as an extra validation step performed online. This step will suggest a questionnaire on an already refined and pre-validated list of innovations as technologies, which would be accepted (or revised) through the previous online consultation step. The outcomes of this online survey are presented in the following section of this deliverable.
3. Offline validation through workshops. This comes as a final validation step, and is addressed mostly to the public sector organisations and regional organisations (SMEs, NGOs, etc.), performing a validation of the online results but having in mind their case's context. Small-scale workshops may take place with the participation of civil servants and IT representatives of public administrations as a means of discussing with the former and validating the insights acquired on societal and public sector needs. Additionally, validation workshop can be organised in order to present and discuss with experts and interested stakeholders the knowledge accumulated around emerging technologies and related innovation solutions.

³⁴ <http://futureofthebook.org/commentpress/>

4 Online Consultation Outcomes

The online consultation that took place between June 2017 and end of July 2017 completes the cycle of activities, organized by the SONNETS consortium with the view to validate the project results. The online consultation that counted in particular with the support and participation of the various stakeholders engaged along the course of the project duration (i.e. the SONNETS Community) has had a twofold goal, i.e. validate the results of the conducted needs' analysis as well as the contents of the proposed Innovation Identification Framework. In the context of this deliverable, the focus is placed on the outcomes of the online consultation with regard to the Innovation Identification Framework, which are presented in the following paragraphs. At the time of preparing this report, these outcomes are based on a sample of 130 participants. The results of the online consultation with regard to the needs' analysis are accordingly reported in the updated version of deliverable D2.2.

The questions addressed to the participants revolve around the use by the respondents of a similar framework for innovation identification, as well as their promptness to use the SONNETS Framework in specific, the most appropriate starting point of the innovation identification process, potential omissions, but also the most important and most difficult to implement steps of the framework. The participants' responses unveil the following interesting findings:

Only 9.1% of the respondents have been using a similar framework for innovation identification in the context of their professional activity in the public sector, whereas the rest of them, i.e. a percentage of 90.1% have claimed not to have similar experience, which potentially indicates a gap concerning the development of guidelines for the promotion of innovation.

Figure 18: Distribution of participants' responses with regard to the use of a framework for innovation identification (Q1)

Figure 19: Distribution of participants’ responses with regard to the starting point of the innovation identification process (Q2)

Assumptions seem, on the other hand, hard to be made, when it comes to defining the right starting point of the innovation identification process, as the respondents’ opinions have differed significantly with answers being almost equally distributed among the two options available, i.e. those of diagnosing the current public sector status, and thus identifying the current relevant needs (54%) and specifying the desired future status of the latter, by setting the respective goals (46%).

Figure 20: Distribution of participants’ responses on potential framework omissions (Q3)

On the side of the Framework's contents and its comprehensiveness, 68%, thereby the majority of the respondents have found the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework sufficient, thus denying the omission of any important aspects; 6% of them have been unsure about it, whereas 26% have brought up additional factors for consideration. Such aspects include among others the political factor, which is though taken into consideration under the feasibility analysis, foreseen in the context of the innovation identification step, the notions of cyber innovation and the digital economy, the perspective of aligning the innovation identification process with R&D programs, as well as those of reducing the size of the state before applying any improvements or innovations, performing changes in senior posts and redefining the criteria of recruiting, and cultivating an innovation culture, as prerequisites to applying the innovation identification framework.

With regard to the most important step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework, the majority of respondents (42%) have voted for the aspect of needs' identification. The latter has been followed by the steps of innovation identification (19%), scenario building (12%) and technology selection and analysis (10%). The technology identification and assessment steps have acquired each a 7% of the respondents' votes, whereas validation has received only 2% of them.

Figure 21: Distribution of participants' responses with regard to the most important step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework (Q4)

Q5. Which step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework do you consider as being the most difficult to implement in the context of the public sector?

Figure 22: Distribution of participants' responses with regard to the most difficult to implement step of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework (Q5)

The image revealed by the online consultation has been drastically different, when the most difficult to implement step of the SONNETS Framework in the context of the public sector has been the focus of the question. In this case, the step of innovation identification has gathered the majority of votes (27%), followed by that of validation (22%). The steps of needs' identification and scenario building have each received an equal percentage of votes (14%), whereas technology identification (2%), technology selection and analysis (9%) and technology assessment (11%) have been considered as the least difficult to implement.

Besides evaluating and reasoning on the Framework, participants have also been prompted to propose additional methods that could be employed to support the goals of the latter. So, besides desk-based research, interviews, focus groups / workshops and the conduction of an online consultation, namely the methods adopted in the context of the SONNETS project, suggestions have brought up as well the options of employing questionnaires, conducting large-scale surveys, leveraging sentiment analysis to sense what citizens at large think in social media and the web, as well as the practices of open brainstorming, crowdsourcing, promoting participatory observation and co-creation and establishing living labs. Further suggestions on the use of lean start-up methodologies and step by step guides to innovation have brought up the aspect of technology and innovation implementation, thus providing new directions for the extension of the SONNETS Framework, while ideas on the use of key target indicators have indicated potential alternatives for post-implementation validation.

Figure 23: Distribution of participants' responses with regard to their willingness to use the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework (Q7)

Last but not least, particularly encouraging have been the results of the online consultation with regard to the participants' willingness to use the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework in the field of their activity, as 83% of the respondents declared to be open and positive towards such an option. Given that the vast majority of respondents (90,1%) claimed not to be using a similar framework, this is quite important, as it brings up both an opportunity to introduce the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework to these people, but also the challenge of properly supporting them so as to use it.

Attention is drawn to the fact that validation by means of the online consultation can be an ongoing process, as both the project research outcomes as well as the survey forms underpinning the collection of feedback by the stakeholders interested have been embedded in a dedicated section of the project section, which is thus anticipated to act as a live document, incorporating any new additions or modifications made.

5 Next Steps

SONNETS aspires to be the start of a decisive step forward in the transformation of the public sector into an innovation leader and innovation breeding carrier, thus, it is the aim of the SONNETS consortium to pursue the constant updating and advancement of the project results beyond the project end, by means of incorporating new feedback and comments by the SONNETS network of stakeholders, as well as by keeping up and taking into account the findings of other similar attempts and initiatives.

As far as its Innovation Identification Framework is concerned, at the end of the project duration and having completed the full range of the foreseen validation activities, the SONNETS consortium is proud to claim a high degree of acceptance of its research outcomes by the targeted stakeholders, as well as the acquisition of new insights and ideas for the framework's further enrichment and extension.

Given these insights and ideas, but also further research conducted on behalf of its members, the SONNETS consortium has already specified a number of directions for the Framework's future improvement. These in brief include:

- The incorporation of additional research methods and practices, such as those of crowdsourcing, social media sensing and web mining.
- The engagement, by means of the development of more elaborate questionnaires, the organization of interviews and focus groups and the exploitation of crowdsourcing approaches, of the general public, not only in the identification of societal needs and technologies, but also in the completion of a SWOT analysis for the identified technologies in each of the vertical domains (e.g. the institutional / capacity development, political, economic, social, infrastructural and environmental domains), foreseen in the impact assessment analysis, taking place in the frame of the innovation identification step of the framework application.
- The enrichment of the feasibility assessment analysis, taking place within the same step with additional assessment dimensions, the gathering of relevant assessments for all identified technologies from several countries and the conduction therefore of cross-country comparisons.
- The extension of the framework towards the direction of applying the identified innovations, by means of incorporating step-by-step guidelines, adapted from lean methodologies and creating a knowledge base for sharing best practices and relevant experiences among the SONNETS network of stakeholders.

The SONNETS consortium has also plans for further collaboration with the stakeholders met during the events and activities, organised by the project in view of the validation of its findings. Among the identified collaboration prospects stand

- the provision of support and guidance to public administrations in the light of applying the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework.
- An attempt to complement the UN E-Government Development Index (EGDI)³⁵, a composite index which assesses e-government development at national level, based on the average of three normalized indices, i.e.
 - a Telecommunications Infrastructure Index (TII), based on data provided by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU),
 - a Human Capital Index (HCI), based on data provided by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and

³⁵ United Nations - Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2016). UNITED NATIONS E-GOVERNMENT SURVEY 2016, New York. Available at: <http://workspace.unpan.org/sites/Internet/Documents/UNPAN97453.pdf>

- an Online Service Index (OSI), based on data collected from an independent survey questionnaire that assesses the national online presence of all 193 United Nations Member States.

The EGDI is used to measure the readiness and capacity of public administrations to use ICT to deliver public services at national level, and thus can benefit from the Framework's rational of investigating the public sector's innovation potential at all national, regional and local levels.

On the other hand, the EGDI itself can be leveraged to enhance the feasibility assessment analysis of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework.

6 Conclusions

What is the purpose of this report?

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The purpose of this report is to describe and explain the “SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework for the Public Sector” which forms the basis of the methodology of SONNETS for collecting, analysing and cross-checking the usability of emerging ICTs in the public sector.

Thus, this framework has been primarily intended to guide activities within the project, but may also be considered as a self-standing methodological aid for supporting the public sector’s ICT transformation.

Which objective of SONNETS does this report pursue?

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SONNETS pursues the objective to provide guidelines and a methodological framework that will help to reshape and transform the public sector into a technology leader and driver of innovation.

This methodology includes the analysis of current and upcoming societal needs as well as the identification and analysis of emerging ICT technologies/trends and the assessment of their innovation potential for the public sector.

This report helps to achieve this objective by elaborating the methodological framework and outlining the respective steps of the SONNETS work plan.

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How does the SONNETS methodology work?

SONNETS pursues the aim to support innovation both *in* the public sector and *through* the public sector as an innovation driver with a focus on other policy domains.

To achieve this objective SONNETS has placed its focus on:

1. Identifying societal needs and trends that need to be met by public sector services:
 - These trends can be collected by using desktop research methods and validated by interviews with experts and by focus groups.
2. Identifying emerging ICT technologies and trends:
 - The technologies can be identified by means of desk-based research as well as by the conduction of interviews with IT experts.
3. Analysing these ICT technologies and trends in terms of their key characteristics and specificities:

- The technology analysis can be performed by using desk-based research as well as experts' interviews and focus groups. The aim of this analysis is to describe the technologies regarding e.g. their usage, scope, mainstream application and forecasted market potential and growth.
- 4. Assessing these ICT technologies regarding their potential to meet societal challenges and public sector needs:
 - This technology assessment includes a SWOT (strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) analysis. Furthermore, these technologies are correlated with the identified societal challenges and needs to assess their relevance for the public sector. Additionally, new innovative solutions can be put forward which may benefit from these ICT technologies.
- 5. Evaluating the innovation potential of these solutions regarding their impact and feasibility
 - The impact of these solutions can be assessed along two dimensions. Firstly, a vertical dimension, which includes e.g. the transformation of the public sector itself (like image modernization, process optimization or political aspects like the participation of citizens) as well as aspects of the public sector as an innovation driver. In the horizontal dimension this assessment includes aspects like the extent of the application or the type of influence.
 - Regarding the feasibility issues like the existing ICT infrastructure, and the legislative framework, the stakeholders IT literacy as well as the political will are to be taken into account.
- 6. Developing scenarios to validate the usability of a specific technology in the public sector:
 - The aim of these scenarios is to forecast the future conditions of the world and to select the solutions that make more sense to be ported into the public sector based on the specification of the most desired and most probable public sector future scenarios.
- 7. Evaluating the overall findings of SONNETS
 - SONNETS proposes a variety of different valuation methods, like online feedback and workshops, to be able to include the insights and opinions of a broad range of experts.

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Which methods does the SONNETS methodology include?

The SONNETS methodology includes desk-based research methods, interviews, focus groups, brainstorming and online consultation.

Which stakeholders have been involved in the process?

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The SONNETS network includes a broad range of experts covering the area of ICT as well as knowledge of the public sector. During the course of the project the experts of this network have been engaged and involved in a number of activities like workshops, interviews or direct feedback. The engagement of the experts has taken primarily place through the establishment of and interaction with two supportive bodies, namely the SONNETS Experts Committee and the SONNETS Advisory Group.

In more detail the SONNETS network includes representatives of the public sector, IT experts, citizen representatives and members of the ICT research community.

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How has this report been used within the project?

This report has been used as the methodological guideline for the work conducted within SONNETS.

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What are the next steps?

The SONNETS consortium foresees the further improvement and extension of the SONNETS Innovation Identification Framework along a number of directions based on the insights and ideas gathered through the project's offline and online validation activities.

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I. Appendix A: Guidelines for Interviews with Privileged Informants (Needs-focused interviews)

In the following sections the reader may find a set of guidelines, developed with the goal of supporting the conduction of interviews with privileged informants (i.e. citizen, business and public sector representatives) towards the identification of societal challenges and public sector needs. The questions have been adapted and customized to the characteristics of each group of interviewees so as to encourage the latter to argue on their own perspectives. The same sets of questions can be used to promote discussions within focus groups.

I.1 Guidelines for interviews with citizen representatives

Barring exceptional circumstances, all questions must be asked. If the interviewee does not expand on the questions him/herself, follow-up questions are provided that can be asked in order to get more expansive answers. Please record the interviews, unless the interviewee specifically asks for them not to be recorded. If the interviewee does not want it to be recorded, please take extensive notes on the interview.

At this time, we are not asking for full transcripts of the interviews. Instead, please provide detailed summaries or reports of the interviews. These summaries should be structured around the questions asked, along with any additional observations or insights that might emerge from the interviews.

Introductory Questions

- 1. Can you briefly describe your profile, i.e., occupation, family etc.**
- 2. Could you describe the ways in which you interact with the public sector (PS)?**

Follow-up questions:

- What do you usually contact PS for?
- How often do you interact with the public sector and at what levels (municipality, state level or national level)?
- How do you approach PS?
- What are the main problems or challenges you encounter in dealing with public sector?

- 3. Since how long have you been interacting with public sector?**

Substantive Questions

- 4. Could you please mention the key needs in your opinion?**

The interviewer should note down all the needs mentioned by the respondent.

- 5. Out of the needs you mentioned, what are the most important needs?**

After the interview, the interviewer should match the needs against the list of macro needs, tick the ones suggested by the interviewee.

6. Could you propose actions/solutions that might be taken to address these needs?

The actions/solutions include both technological and non-technological solutions. Please ask for a solution corresponding to each need.

Follow-up question:

- Can you please provide some real life examples or cases where such solutions have been implemented or are being implemented?

After the interview, interviewer should check the list of innovation items, tick the ones suggested by the respondent. If the action proposed is not included in the list of innovation actions, please add it to the list for future references.

7. Apart from the needs mentioned on the list, are there any other major needs that are emerging and could impact you in the coming years?

Follow-up questions:

- How can these needs be addressed?
- Who can address these needs?
- Do you think these future needs will have a positive or negative impact?
- What do you think the overall repercussions of these new needs will be for public administration in your country?

I.2 Guidelines for interviews with business representatives

Barring exceptional circumstances, all questions must be asked. If the interviewee does not expand on the questions him/herself, follow-up questions are provided that can be asked in order to get more expansive answers. Please record the interviews, unless the interviewee specifically asks for them not to be recorded. If the interviewee does not want it to be recorded, please take extensive notes on the interview.

At this time, we are not asking for full transcripts of the interviews. Instead, please provide detailed summaries or reports of the interviews. These summaries should be structured around the questions asked, along with any additional observations or insights that might emerge from the interviews.

Introductory Questions

1. What is your business about? What are the main business activities you undertake?

2. How long are you in this business?

Follow-up questions:

- Has your business changed at all over time?
- In what way?

3. Do you interact with the public sector? If yes, could you describe the ways in which you interact with the public sector (PS)?

Follow-up questions:

- What do you usually contact PS for?
- How often do you interact with the public sector and at what levels (municipality, state level or national level)?
- How do you approach PS?
- What are the main problems or challenges you encounter in dealing with public sector?

Substantive Questions

4. Could you please mention the key needs in your opinion?

The interviewer should note down all the needs mentioned by the respondent.

5. Out of the needs you mentioned, what are the most important needs?

After the interview, the interviewer should match the needs against the list of macro needs, tick the ones suggested by the interviewee.

6. Could you propose actions/solutions that might be taken to address these needs?

The actions/solutions include both technological and non-technological solutions. Please ask for a solution corresponding to each need.

Follow-up question:

- Can you please provide some real life examples or cases where such solutions have been implemented or are being implemented?

After the interview, interviewer should check the list of innovation items, tick the ones suggested by the respondent. If the action proposed is not included in the list of innovation actions, please add it to the list for future references.

7. Apart from the needs mentioned on the list, are there any other major needs that are emerging and could impact you in the coming years?

Follow-up questions:

- How can these needs be addressed?
- Who can address these needs?
- Do you think these future needs will have a positive or negative impact?
- What do you think the overall repercussions of these new needs will be for public administration in your country?

I.3 Guidelines for interviews with public sector representatives

Barring exceptional circumstances, all questions must be asked. If the interviewee does not expand on the questions him/herself, follow-up questions are provided that can be asked in order to get more expansive answers. Please record the interviews, unless the interviewee specifically asks for them not to be recorded. If the interviewee does not want it to be recorded, please take extensive notes on the interview.

At this time, we are not asking for full transcripts of the interviews. Instead, please provide detailed summaries or reports of the interviews. These summaries should be structured around the questions asked, along with any additional observations or insights that might emerge from the interviews.

Introductory Questions

1. Could you please briefly describe your role/the role of your organisation?

2. How long have you worked in this role?

Follow-up question:

- Has your role changed at all over time?
- In what way?

Substantive Questions

3. Could you please mention the key needs for your organization in your opinion?

The interviewer should note down all the needs mentioned by the respondent.

4. Out of the needs you mentioned, what are the most important needs?

After the interview, the interviewer should match the needs against the list of macro needs, tick the ones suggested by the interviewee.

5. Could you propose innovation actions/solutions that might be taken to address those needs?

The actions/solutions include both technological and non-technological solutions. Please ask for a solution corresponding to each need.

Follow-up:

- Can you please provide some real life examples or cases where such solutions have been implemented or are being implemented?

After the interview, interviewer should check the list of innovation items, tick the ones suggested by the respondent. If the action proposed is not included in the list of innovation actions, please add it to the list for future references.

6. Can you pick the policy domains necessary to address the societal needs and trends?

At this point, interviewees should be shown the list of policy domains, so that they can match the policy domains against the key identified needs. If some policy domains are not mentioned, interviewees should be asked for their inputs. It is possible that a key need falls under the purview of multiple policy domains. The interviewees should be asked to map multiple policy domains, wherever relevant.

7. Apart from the needs mentioned on the list, are there any other major needs that are emerging and could impact you in the coming years?

Follow-up questions:

- How can these needs be addressed?
- Who can address these needs?
- Do you think these future needs will have a positive or negative impact?

II. Appendix B: Guidelines for Interviews with IT Experts (Technology-focused interviews)

The following questionnaire has been designed in order to guide the conduction of interviews with IT Experts. The same sets of questions can be used to foster discussions within focus groups.

Introductory Questions:

- 1. Can you briefly describe your profile, i.e. your occupation, the field(s) of expertise, your interest in ICT, etc.?**

Main Questions:

- 2. In your opinion, which are the most important technologies / technological trends that could impact the public sector in the following (five) years?**

Follow-up Questions:

- Which are the most important technologies / technological trends that could improve the operation of the public sector in the following years?
- Which are the ones that could transform the public sector into an innovation driver?
- Which are your predictions on the growth or market potential of these technologies?

The interviewer should note down all the technologies / technological trends mentioned by the respondent and map them against the axes of “i. public sector modernization” and “ii. public sector as an innovation driver”. Additionally, the interviewer should note down the expert’s quantitative or qualitative judgement on the growth of each technology identified.

- 3. Which are the societal needs / needs of the public sector that could be addressed through the use of these technologies?**

The interviewer should note down at least one or more needs for each technology / trend identified.

- 4. Could you please expand on the way in which each of these technologies / trends could benefit the public sector / businesses / citizens?**

Follow-up Questions:

- Which are the specific (policy) domains (e.g. political, economic, social, environmental, etc.), these technologies will have an impact on?
- Which will be the extent of that impact (e.g. individual cases, local, regional, national, international level)?
- Is this impact direct or indirect?

5. How feasible do you consider the adoption of these technologies / trends by the public sector?

Follow-up Questions:

- Are these technologies mature enough and ready for adoption?
- Does the public sector already possess the necessary infrastructure and know-how for their adoption? Is the necessary legislative framework already in place?
- How would you evaluate the readiness of the stakeholders involved, in terms of their educational level, skills, income, etc.?

6. Do you see any relevant costs/risks/threats generated by their adoption?

7. Could you propose relevant services and applications to put these technologies/ trends in practice, i.e. to exploit the former for addressing specific needs?

Follow-up Questions:

- What is the type of innovation these solutions stand for (e.g. service innovation, service delivery innovation, organizational innovation, etc.)?
- Can you provide real life examples or cases where such services / applications have been implemented or are being implemented?

Here, the interviewer should use the list of innovation actions, derived from WP2, to tick the ones suggested by the respondent and add the technology applications or innovation actions not already included.

III. Appendix C: Technology / Trend Analysis Template

Technology / Technological Trend	
Identifier	<i>TE#x or TT#x</i>
Type	<p><i>e.g.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for technologies: "self-standing technology" or "resulting from the technological convergence of the fields of ..." - for trends: "based on the technology of ..."
Description	
Mainstream Domains of Application	<i>e.g. Enterprise Sector, Manufacturing, Telecommunications, etc.</i>
Related Market Potential/Forecasted Growth	
Related Terms	
Source(s)	

IV. Appendix D: Technology / Trend Assessment Template

Technology / Technological Trend	
Identifier	<i>TE#x or TT#x</i>
SWOT Analysis	
Relevant Needs	
Potential Applications / Services	
Existing solutions / products / services	